

Investigations on the Fundamental Domain of the Modular Group

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to understand the fundamental domain of the modular group, and investigate the nature of transformations that map points outside the fundamental domain to points inside the fundamental domain of the modular group. This has also been verified computationally: the upper half complex plane has been divided into appropriate regions and a Python simulation has been run to verify the transformations that maps the points inside the fundamental domain for each region. This enriches our understanding of modular groups, which is crucial to understand modular forms, which have wide-ranging applications in the fields of mathematics, physics and even beyond. The sheer richness of the theory of modular forms provides powerful tools for understanding certain physical and mathematical phenomena where modular symmetry naturally arises, such as in string theory, number theory and cryptography. In physics, modular forms have made it possible to study various models of interaction of elementary particles (via two-dimensional conformal field theories), which is of significant help in quantum field theory and string theory research.

Keywords: Group theory, Group action, Modular group, Modular symmetry, Fundamental domain, Modular transformations

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1 Theoretical Background and Key Definitions

1.1 Groups and Symmetries

The **modular group** and **modular forms**¹ combine two different fields in mathematics: complex analysis and group theory, and also involve number theory, algebraic geometry and probably many more areas of mathematics. Now, just like real analysis is the study of real numbers, complex analysis is the study of complex numbers. In real analysis, we deal with numbers lying on the one-dimensional real line, hence there are only two directions from which we can approach a point (from the left or from the right). However, complex numbers are represented as points on a two-dimensional plane; the horizontal axis represents the real number, and the vertical axis represents the imaginary axis, which contains the imaginary numbers, namely real numbers multiplied by i , where $i = -1$. For a complex number $z = a + bi$, we say that a is the real part of z , written $Re(z)$, and b the imaginary part of z , written $Im(z)$. Also, we denote the upper half complex plane by H (H consists of all complex numbers z with $Im(z) > 0$; and the points lying *on* the real axis are not part of H , since $Im(z)$ is strictly greater than zero). In a two-dimensional plane, we can approach a point from infinitely many directions. If a complex function is complex differentiable² in some region C of the complex plane, it is said to be analytic or holomorphic in that region.

Group theory, on the other hand, is the field of mathematics that studies abstract symmetries³. A **symmetry** is essentially a transformation under which the object being transformed remains unchanged in some respect(s). For example, if the three vertices of the triangle are indistinguishable (not marked separately), rotating an equilateral triangle by 120 degrees does not change the orientation of the triangle (so here, it is the orientation that remains symmetric under the transformation). Similarly, flipping the equilateral triangle along a perpendicular line joining one of its vertices does not change its orientation either. And if we leave the equilateral triangle as it is (do nothing to it), again its orientation does not change. All these transformations form a part of the symmetry group of the equilateral triangle; the symmetry group of an object is the group of all transformations under which the object remains unchanged in some respect(s).

¹ Modular forms are complex functions defined corresponding to the modular group, that follow certain conditions.

² $f(z)$ is complex differentiable if its derivative with respect to the complex variable z is finite and well-defined.

³ From a physics perspective, symmetry is a more abstract parameter whose effects are often not explicitly apparent; it is nevertheless a very important concept in physics.

A **group** is not just any collection of elements. Mathematically, a group is a set of mathematical objects (integers, matrices etc.) with the operation $*$ that satisfies the following conditions:

- If $a * b = c$ for some a and b in the group, c must also belong to the group (**closure**)
- There is an identity element e such that $a * e = a$ for all elements a in the group (**identity**)
- For each element a , there is an inverse element c , such that $a * c = c * a = e$ (**inverse**)
- For elements a, b and c in the group, $a * (b * c) = (a * b) * c$ (**associativity**).

This axiomatic definition of a group enables us to effectively study more abstract symmetries than the familiar shapes of polygons.

Figure 1: Symmetries of an equilateral triangle. (Source: Quanta Magazine.)

In the case of the equilateral triangle, it is clear to see why all transformations that maintain the orientational symmetry will form a group. The transformation representing the act of doing nothing to the triangle is the identity transformation, and we can always reverse these transformations (we can rotate the triangle by

120 degrees clockwise and do the same counterclockwise). The order of these transformations does not matter either, because after each transformation, the orientation remains unchanged. Finally, any two of these transformations, taken together as a third transformation, will also clearly not break the orientational symmetry. Thus, these transformations form a group (the symmetry group of the equilateral triangle), since they satisfy all the four conditions of a group mentioned above.

The next question is, what do the elements of the symmetry group look like? Are they integers? Or complex numbers? Or what? Matrices can represent any linear transformation, including the above transformations. In order to get an idea, let us roughly think of every state (orientation) of the system (equilateral triangle) as a point on a two-dimensional plane (for simplicity), and can be represented by a column matrix. Then, every transformation of the system from the initial state to a final state can be represented by a square matrix (called the **transformation matrix**). Let the initial and final states A and B are represented by the matrices:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, a_1 (b_1) and a_2 (b_2) are the horizontal and vertical coordinates of the state A (B), which is just a point on a two-dimensional space defined by a horizontal and a vertical axis. Let us now define a transformation matrix T that transforms the system from state A to state B :

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

Mathematically, the above transformation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us now illustrate, with two examples, how matrices can represent transformations like translation and rotation. First, consider the point $A(1,1)$, represented by the column matrix:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, we pre-multiplying (multiplying from the left) this column matrix using the transformation matrix:

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This gives us:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The transformed point is $B(3,1)$, which is just the original point $A(1,1)$ translated two units to the right (horizontally).

Figure 2: Translation. (Generated using Desmos.)

Now, let us transform the point $A(2,3)$, represented by a column matrix as before, using the transformation matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

This gives us:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 \\ 3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3 \\ -2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The transformed point, $B(3, -2)$, is obtained after a rotation (about the origin) of the line joining the origin to the point $A(1,1)$.

Figure 3: Rotation. (Generated using Desmos.)

The above discussion serves as a very basic introduction to the concept of symmetry, and why group theory plays such an important role here. Now, we will briefly discuss some important mathematical concepts and definitions, before we move on to modular groups.

1.2 General Linear Group

The **general linear group**⁴ of degree n is the set of all $n \times n$ invertible matrices (or matrices with non-zero determinants), together with the operation of ordinary matrix multiplication. In other words, it is a group under the operation of matrix multiplication. This forms a group, because the product of two invertible matrices is again invertible (closure). The product of two invertible matrices is invertible because the determinant of an invertible matrix is non-zero, which means the determinant of the product of two matrices is the product of the determinants of the individual matrices and the product of two non-zero numbers can never be zero. Also, matrix multiplication is associative (associativity); the inverse of an invertible matrix exists by definition (inverse); and the identity matrix is the identity element of the group (identity). All the four conditions required to form a group are, thus, satisfied.

The group is called a general linear group because the columns (and also the rows) of an invertible matrix are linearly independent, hence the vectors/points they define are in general linear position (recall the two examples we discussed above, where a point on a two-dimensional plane was represented by a two-dimensional column matrix), and matrices in the general linear group take points in general linear position to other points in general linear position. General linear group (or just general group) is basically a set of points arranged in such a manner in an n -dimensional space such that no set of $(n + 1)$ points lie in any possible n -dimensional hyperplane (basically a generalization of a two-dimensional plane in three-dimensional space to mathematical spaces of arbitrary dimensions; for example, a point is a hyperplane in one-dimensional space, a line is a hyperplane in two-dimensional space, and a plane is a hyperplane in three-dimensional space). If no *three* points lie on the same line, the set of points form a general linear group in a *two*-dimensional space. Similarly, if no *two* points coincide, they form a general linear group in a *one*-dimensional space; and if no *four* points lie on the same plane, they form a general group in a *three*-dimensional space.

⁴ $GL(n, F)$ denotes the general group of dimension n over the field F . The field F could be the set of real numbers, or the set of complex numbers, etc. For example, the general linear group over R (the set of real numbers), which is the group of $n \times n$ invertible matrices whose elements are real numbers, with matrix multiplication being the group operation, is denoted by $GL(n, R)$.

1.3 Special Linear Group

The **special linear group**, written $SL(n, F)$, is the subgroup of the general linear group $GL(n, F)$ consisting only of matrices with determinant one. The set of all matrices with determinant one from the group $GL(n, F)$ is itself a group, because the determinant of the product of two matrices is the product of the determinants of the individual matrices. Hence, if we multiply any two matrices from $SL(n, F)$, which by definition have determinants one, the determinant of the product matrix will also be one ($1 \times 1 = 1$), and the product matrix will also belong to $SL(n, F)$, satisfying the closure property. The other three properties of a group, namely associativity, inverse and identity, will always be satisfied by a set of $n \times n$ invertible matrices over the matrix multiplication operation, as long as all of their determinants are non-zero.

1.4 Normal Subgroups, Cosets and Quotient Groups

Let N be a subgroup of group G , where the group operation is multiplication. This means N consists of some elements of G , and is itself a group. N is said to be a **normal subgroup** of G , iff for every x in G and for every y in N , $xy = yx$. This does not necessarily mean that G is an Abelian group⁵.

Clearly, y belongs to N automatically implies y belongs to G , since N is a subgroup of G . Now, if N be any subgroup of group G , and x be any arbitrary element of G , Nx is a **right coset** of N in G , and xN is a **left coset** of N in G . In the special case that N is a normal subgroup of G , there is no difference between the left and right cosets of N in G .

Now, a **quotient group** is the set of all cosets of a normal subgroup of a group. If G is a group and N is a normal subgroup of G (group operation is multiplication), then the set of all cosets of N in G is a quotient group, written G/N (“ G modulo N ”). Mathematically, from the definition of cosets and normal subgroups, we see that $G/N = \{Nx, x \in G\}$. The elements of this set, which is G/N , are in the form of cosets, Nx_1, Nx_2, \dots, Nx_n , if there are n elements in G : $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$. This set G/N forms a group (we call it the quotient group).

Let us now show why G/N forms a group. First, let x and y belong to G , and Nx and Ny belong to G/N . Now, since N is a normal subgroup of G , $(Nx)(Ny) = (Nx)(yN) = N(xy)N$. Now, for $z = xy$, we have:

$$(Nx)(Ny) = N(xy)N = NzN = NNz$$

⁵ Every element of an Abelian group commutes with every other element of the same group, which means $xy = yx$ for all x, y , where x and y are arbitrary elements belonging to the Abelian group. Here, we have, for every x in G and for every y in N , $xy = yx$. Even if G is not an Abelian group, this condition may be satisfied by *some* y , which form a normal subgroup of G .

Now, since N is a subgroup of G , NN is a subset of N by virtue of N being a group and thus satisfying the closure property. And N is also a subset of NN . Say y belongs to N and e is the identity element of N ; hence e also belongs to N , and $y = ey$ belongs to NN . This means NN is a subset of N , and N is also a subset of NN , which inevitably means $NN = N$. This gives us:

$$(Nx)(Ny) = NNz = Nz$$

Now, since x and y belong to G , and G is a group (under multiplication), $xy = z$ must also belong to G . Also, $(Nx)(Ny) = Nz$, and since z belongs to G , Nz belongs to G/N , which means $(Nx)(Ny)$ belongs to G/N , if Nx and Ny belong to G/N , as we have initially assumed. Thus, the elements of G/N satisfy the closure property. G/N also satisfies the associative property, the proof of which is skipped here. Now consider some x belongs to G , Nx belongs to G/N . $(Nx)N = (Nx)(Ne)$, where e is the identity element of G .

$$(Nx)N = (Nx)(Ne) = (NN)(xe) = Nx$$

We have used $NN = N$ and $xe = x$ (since x belongs to G , and e is the identity element of G). Now, we further modify this expression:

$$\begin{aligned} (Nx)N &= Nx = N(ex) = (NN)(ex) = N(Ne)x = N(eN)x = (Ne)(Nx) \\ &= N(Nx) \end{aligned}$$

Since $(Nx)N = N(Nx) = Nx$, N is the identity element of G/N . Finally, if x is an element of G , x' is also an element of G , where x' is the inverse element in G which must exist since G is a group. Thus, Nx and Nx' both belong to G/N .

$$(Nx)(Nx') = N(xN)x' = N(Nx)x' = (NN)(xx') = Ne = N$$

Above we have used $xN = Nx$ (since N is a normal subgroup of G), $NN = N$ as shown previously, $xx' = e$ and $Ne = N$. Note that a subgroup has the same identity as its parent group. Let y_1 and y_2 belong to N , which means they belong to G as well. Further, let y_2 be the inverse of y_1 , which is allowed since N is a group. Now, $y_1y_2 = e_N$, but since y_1 and y_2 are elements of G as well, y_1y_2 must also be equal to e_G , which means e_N and e_G are the same, where e_N is the identity element of N and e_G is the identity element of G . Similarly, we got $(Nx')(Nx) = N$, and we have already seen that N is the identity element of G/N . Thus, Nx' is the inverse element in G/N . This completes the proof that G/N forms a group.

1.5 Projective Space

A **projective space** is an extension of Euclidean space with points at infinity. In a projective space, two lines always intersect (parallel lines intersect at infinity). Suppose we have a classical one-dimensional line – the x -axis itself (the blue line

in the figure below). The corresponding projective line (the red line) will be a circle touching the classical line at one point.

Figure 4: Projective space. (Generated using Paint.)

For every point on the classical line, there is a unique point on the projective line (one-to-one correspondence), and we define the point O on the projective line as both positive and negative infinity. Consider the point P (-1) on the classical line. To find its corresponding point P' on the projective line, we simply join P and O with a straight line. The point P' , where the line segment PO intersects the projective line (at a point other than O , of course) is the projective coordinates of the point P . As P moves closer and closer to negative infinity (toward the far left), P' will move closer and closer to O . Similarly, if we choose P close to positive infinity, again P' will approach O , albeit from the opposite direction. This is why the point O corresponds to both positive and negative infinity. The projective coordinates of O can be written as $[1:0]$ (sometimes written $[1,0]$, and read “1 over 0”) or equivalently $[-1:0]$, since $1/0$ is positive infinity and $-1/0$ is negative infinity. The projective coordinates of P' is $[-1:1]$; the first coordinate corresponds to -1 on the classical line, and the second coordinate, 1 , is common to all points on the projective line (except point O , where the second coordinate is zero). The projective coordinates of the point $+2$ on the classical line would be $[2:1]$ and so on. This roughly translates to dividing the first coordinate by one. This is how homogeneous coordinates are defined. The homogenous coordinates of the point x lying on a one-dimensional line will be of the form $[x:1]$ (or equivalently $[2x:2]$, $[3x:3]$ and so on; essentially we are dividing the first coordinate by the second coordinate, and the division should yield the original coordinate x). $[x:0]$ corresponds to infinity and $[0:0]$ is not allowed (x cannot be zero), since $0/0$ is not defined. Extending to two dimensions, the homogenous coordinates of the point (x,y) lying on a two-dimensional plane will be of the form $[x:y:1]$, and so on. Also, two projective lines in the same plane must meet at least at one point.

Let us now look at the formal definition of projective space. For a vector space V defined over some field F , the projective space $P(V)$ is the set of equivalence classes⁶ of $V \setminus \{0\}$ (we consider all V except 0) under the equivalence relation $x \sim kx$, for some non-zero k in F . If a basis of V has been chosen, the projective coordinates of a point P are the coordinates in this basis of any element of the corresponding equivalence class. These coordinates are denoted $[x_0 : \dots : x_n]$. Now, if $[x_0 : \dots : x_n]$ are projective coordinates of a point, then $[kx_0 : \dots : kx_n]$ are also projective coordinates of the same point, for any non-zero k in F . This means if we scale all the projective coordinates of a point by some constant, non-zero scalar, the new coordinates describe the same point. Consider the real projective space RP^2 , which is basically a space of two-dimensional lines in R^3 (three-dimensions), just like in the figure above (Figure 4), RP^1 is a space of one-dimensional points in R^2 , forming a circle.⁷ For RP^2 , we start with a three-dimensional sphere. In this sphere, the “north pole” and “south pole” of the sphere represent the same point, and in fact, *all* diametrically opposite points are equivalent; they are related by just a scalar factor. Hence, we glue these points together, and we are left with a single hemisphere. We also need to glue the diametrically opposite points lying on the equator, since they are also linked by a scalar. After doing all this, we get a complicated geometrical structure – RP^2 – which is difficult to visualize.

1.6 Projective Linear Group

The **projective linear group** (also called projective general linear group PGL) is the induced **group action**⁸ of the general linear group of a vector space $V - GL(V)$ – on the associated projective space $P(V)$. In terms of quotient groups, $PGL(V = GL(V)/Z(V)$, where $Z(V)$ is the center⁹ of $GL(V)$. The elements of the projective linear group can be understood as “tilting the plane” along one of the axes, and then projecting all the points in this tilted plane to the original plane.¹⁰

⁶ A set can be divided into equivalence classes, and two elements belong to the same equivalent class iff they are equivalent. Formally, the equivalence class of an element a belonging to a set X is defined $[a] = \{x \in X \mid a \sim x\}$, where \sim denotes an equivalence relation on X .

⁷ In general, RP^n is defined as $(R^{n+1} \setminus \{0\}) / (x \sim kx)$, or the set of equivalence classes of R^{n+1} , excluding 0, over the equivalence relation $x \sim kx$.

⁸ A group is said to act on a set when a certain transformation of that set is consistent with the group structure. Mathematically, a group action of a group G (let the group operation be $*$) on a set S is some function $f: G \times S \rightarrow S$ satisfying $e * s = s$ and $g * (h * s) = (gh) * s$, where e is the identity element of G (hence e belongs to G), s belongs to S , and g and h belongs to G . In simpler terms, a group action refers to an element of that group ‘acting’ on a set of points and transforming them, like a matrix belonging to the rotation group can rotate a set of points on a plane.

⁹ The center of a group G , denoted $Z(G)$, is the set of *all* elements of that group that commute with *every* element of G ; $Z(G) = \{z \in G \mid \forall g \in G, zg = gz\}$.

¹⁰ This is a group action, in this case a function $f: GL(V) \times P(V) \rightarrow P(V)$; $GL(V) \times P(V)$ corresponds to the rotation transformation which rotates the projective plane $P(V)$ along one of the axes, and then we project to the original plane $P(V)$, hence $f: GL(V) \times P(V) \rightarrow P(V)$.

1.7 Projective Special Linear Group

The **projective special linear group** over V , denoted $PSL(V)$, is the induced action of the special linear group $SL(V)$ on the projective space $P(V)$. $PSL(V) = SL(V)/SZ(V)$, where $SZ(V)$ is the center of $SL(V)$. It is obvious that the center of $SL(V)$ is $\{I, -I\}$, where I is the identity matrix. The identity matrix and its negative matrix are the only invertible matrices that give the same result, regardless of whether they are left-multiplied or right-multiplied with an arbitrary matrix belonging to $SL(V)$.¹¹ However, $IM = MI$ and $(-I)M = M(-I)$, for some matrix M belonging to $SL(V)$. For the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

to belong to $SZ(V)$, it must satisfy the conditions $a = d, b = c = 0$ and of course, the determinant $ad - bc = 1$ (since it belongs to the special linear group). Combining the above conditions, we get $a^2 = 1$, which means $a = d = \pm 1$, and $b = c = 0$. This means the identity matrix I and its negative $-I$ belong to $SZ(V)$.

1.8 Linear Fractional Transformations

A **linear transformation** can be represented by some function between vector spaces that preserve the structure of the space (hence, linear). An invertible transformation of the form $z \rightarrow (az + b)/(cz + d)$, such that the numerator and denominator of the fraction $(az + b)$ and $(cz + d)$ are linear functions of z , is a **linear fractional transformation**. A linear fractional transformation can also be defined as the projective line over a ring A .¹² When A is a commutative ring (multiplication is commutative), then a linear fractional transformation has the form $z \rightarrow (az + b)/(cz + d)$, where a, b, c, d are elements of A such that $ad - bc$ is a unit of A .¹³ An important property of linear fractional transformations is that they preserve cross-ratios.¹⁴ Mathematically, if a linear fractional transformation maps four distinct points z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4 to four distinct points $\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4$ respectively, then:

$$\frac{(z_1 - z_3)(z_2 - z_4)}{(z_2 - z_3)(z_1 - z_4)} = \frac{(\omega_1 - \omega_3)(\omega_2 - \omega_4)}{(\omega_2 - \omega_3)(\omega_1 - \omega_4)}$$

¹¹ Matrix multiplication is not commutative, in general.

¹² A ring is a special type of field where multiplication need not be commutative and multiplicative inverses need not exist; a field is a set on which addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division are defined and behave just as they do for rational and real numbers.

¹³ This means $(ad - bc)$ has a multiplicative inverse in A . Since A is a ring, multiplicative inverses need not exist for all elements of A .

¹⁴ A cross-ratio is a number associated with a list of four collinear points, particularly points on a projective line.

If one of the points z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4 is the point at infinity (in context of projective space), then the cross-ratio has to be defined by taking the appropriate limit; for example suppose $z_4 = \infty$, then the cross-ratio of z_1, z_2, z_3, ∞ is simply:

$$\frac{(z_1 - z_3)}{(z_2 - z_3)}$$

The projective general linear group $PGL(2, F)$ can be interpreted as the set of fractional linear transformations with coefficients in F . Points on the projective line over F correspond to pairs from F^2 (since $n = 2$), with two pairs (one pair corresponds to one point in a two-dimensional space) being equivalent when they are proportional. When the second coordinate is non-zero, a point can be represented by $[z, 1]$. Thus, when $ad - bc \neq 0$, the action of $PGL(2, F)$ is by linear transformation:

$$[z, 1] \begin{pmatrix} a & c \\ b & d \end{pmatrix} = [az + b, cz + d] = \left[\frac{az + b}{cz + d}, 1 \right]$$

Since $PGL(2, F)$ means the action of $GL(2, F)$ on the associated projective space $P(V)$, the transformation above, in which we essentially multiply the projective coordinates $[z, 1]$ with the matrix (say, M), represents an element of $PGL(2, F)$. The 2×2 matrix M is invertible since its determinant $ad - bc \neq 0$; thus it belongs to $GL(2, F)$. After the first step in the above transformation, we get $[az + b, cz + d]$, which can be equivalently written as $[az + b/cz + d, 1]$. Note that in the above representation, we have denoted $[z, 1]$ as a 1×2 row matrix, and *post-multiplied* (multiplied from the right) it with M , which is the transpose of the matrix¹⁵ M' :

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus, an equivalent representation of the above transformation is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} az + b \\ cz + d \end{pmatrix} = \left[\frac{az + b}{cz + d}, 1 \right]$$

Since two matrices A (order $m \times n$) and B (order $p \times q$) can be multiplied iff $n = p$, we must be careful about the order of multiplication, the choice of the transformation matrix (M or M') and whether we represent the point $[z, 1]$ using a row matrix or a column matrix.

¹⁵ If $M' \in GL(2, F)$, $M \in GL(2, F)$ as well, because the transpose of an invertible matrix is also invertible and the determinant of a matrix is the same as the determinant of its transpose.

2 The Fundamental Domain of the Modular Group

2.1 The Modular Group

The modular group is the quotient of the special linear group $SL(2, Z)$ over the set of integers Z by its center $SZ(V)$, which is $\{I, -I\}$, where I is the identity matrix of order two. Mathematically, the modular group is $\Gamma = SL(2, Z)/SZ(V)$. Alternatively, we can define the modular group as the projective special linear group¹⁶ $PSL(2, Z)$ of 2×2 matrices with integer coefficients and determinant one. The modular group acts on the upper half of the complex plane by fractional linear transformations of the form:

$$z \mapsto \frac{az + b}{cz + d}$$

where a, b, c, d are integers, and $ad - bc = 1$. In other words, the modular group consists of all the 2×2 matrices of the form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

where a, b, c, d are integers, and $ad - bc = 1$ (determinant is unity). The group operation of the modular group is the usual matrix multiplication.

The modular group $SL(2, Z)$ can be generated by the two transformations S and T (called the **generators** of the modular group), where:

$$S: z \mapsto (-1/z)$$

and

$$T: z \mapsto z + 1$$

Geometrically, S represents inversion in the unit circle (with its center at the origin) on the complex plane, followed by reflection with respect to the imaginary axis; whereas T represents a unit translation to the right. Every element in the modular group can be represented by the composition of different integer powers of the transformation matrices S and T .

S and T obey the relations $S^4 = I$ and $S^2 = (ST)^3 = -I$ (I is the identity matrix); and they form a complete set of relations. We can use the presentation method to write the modular group as shown:

$$\Gamma \cong \langle S, T \mid S^4 = I, S^2 = (ST)^3 \rangle$$

¹⁶ Sometimes, the special linear group $SL(2, Z)$ itself is defined as the modular group, and not the corresponding projective special linear group.

$\{S, T\}$ is the set of generators of Γ ; every element of the group can be written as a product of some powers of these generators, provided the generators S and T follow the relations among the generators: $S^4 = I$, $S^2 = (ST)^3$. For example, $T^l S^m T^n$ represents an element of the modular group, where l , m and n are distinct integers. It is not necessary that we take the product of three matrices, more generally it is the product of infinitely many powers of S and T ($\dots S^{n_1} T^{n_2} S^{n_3} T^{n_4} S^{n_5} T^{n_6} \dots$, where $n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5, n_6$ etc. are all distinct integers). This product represents an element of the modular group.¹⁷ Now, for a valid choice of the powers of S and T , we see that S itself also belongs to Γ , since S is essentially $S^1 T^0$ (any matrix raised to the power zero is the identity matrix of the same order). The second order identity matrix $I = S^0 T^0$ is also a member of Γ , which is in fact the identity element of the group.¹⁸

2.2 Fundamental Pairs of Periods

A **fundamental pair of periods** is an ordered pair of complex numbers that defines a lattice in the complex plane. This type of lattice is the underlying object with which modular forms are defined. Basically, a fundamental pair of periods is a pair of complex numbers (ω_1, ω_2) such that their ratio ω_1/ω_2 is *not* real. If we express these complex numbers as vectors in R^2 (the two-dimensional coordinate system with the x -values corresponding to the real part of the complex number and the y -values to the imaginary part), then ω_1 and ω_2 are linearly independent. Note that to define a two-dimensional lattice, we need to specify at least two vectors (the basis vectors). Then we can take infinitely many parallel copies of both these vectors and extend them in all directions to form the lattice. And since these vectors form a basis, they must be linearly independent. In other words, if $\omega_1 = a + ib$ and $\omega_2 = c + id$ (i being the imaginary number), $a/b \neq c/d$. However, it can easily be shown that for the ratio ω_1/ω_2 to be real (for the imaginary part of the division to be zero), $a/b = c/d$. This is why ω_1/ω_2 must not be real.¹⁹

¹⁷ Clearly, the modular group has an infinite number of elements, since we can construct an infinite number of 2×2 matrices with integer coefficients and determinant one. In general, each element can be represented by a product of different integer powers of S and T , in different orders. Also note that although matrix multiplication is associative, it is *not* commutative. Hence, $T^l S^m T^n$ is not the same as $T^{l+n} S^m$ and so on. This is why we use powers of S and T alternatively in the product.

¹⁸ It is not exactly correct to say that I is the identity element of the modular group. This is because $-I$ could also be a valid choice; but the identity element must be unique. If we are talking about $SL(2, Z)$, then I is the identity element. However in $PSL(2, Z)$, both I and $-I$ are considered equivalent (recall our discussion on projective spaces), and this resolves the problem.

¹⁹ If this ratio is real, then ω_1 and ω_2 would be linearly dependent, meaning one is a scalar multiple of the other, and hence both of them would point in the exact same direction (both of them would lie on the same line). Hence, no two-dimensional lattice could be formed.

Figure 5: A two-dimensional lattice. (Source: Wikipedia.)

The lattice (color: cyan) shown above is generated by ω_1 and ω_2 , two vectors (color: blue) on the complex plane. The parallelogram (outlined in blue) with vertices $(0, \omega_1, \omega_1 + \omega_2, \omega_2)$, is called the fundamental parallelogram. There are no lattice points lying in the interior of the fundamental parallelogram. While a fundamental pair generates a lattice, a lattice does not have a unique fundamental pair; in fact, an infinite number of fundamental pairs correspond to the same lattice. The lattice generated by ω_1 and ω_2 is defined as

$$\Lambda = \{m\omega_1 + n\omega_2 \mid m, n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

provided ω_1/ω_2 is not real. Basically, we are talking about the set of all the points of the lattice, which can be obtained by taking all possible linear combinations of ω_1 and ω_2 . Clearly, there are infinitely many possible fundamental pairs, for the infinitely many values and combinations of m and n . Two pairs of complex numbers (ω_1, ω_2) and (α_1, α_2) are equivalent if they generate the same lattice, which demands $\Lambda(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \Lambda(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$. Mathematically, two pairs of complex numbers (ω_1, ω_2) and (α_1, α_2) are equivalent iff there exists a 2 X 2 matrix belonging to the modular group, say M :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

such that:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

This can also be expressed as:

$$\alpha_1 = a\omega_1 + b\omega_2$$

$$\alpha_2 = c\omega_1 + d\omega_2$$

The integers a , b , c and d can be chosen arbitrarily as long as they satisfy the condition $ad - bc = 1$, since the matrix M belongs to the modular group. This shows that elements of the modular group provide a symmetry on a two-dimensional lattice. The elements of the modular group transform (ω_1, ω_2) to (α_1, α_2) in such a way that the lattice they describe is the same. This lattice is said to exhibit **modular symmetry** under the transformation $(\omega_1, \omega_2) \rightarrow (\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$. Note that (ω_1, ω_2) and (α_1, α_2) are points on the complex plane, and clearly, they are not the same point. Hence, it is not these points that show modular symmetry. It is the lattice they generate that remains unchanged under a **modular transformation**.

Figure 6: Both the blue and red fundamental parallelograms describe the same lattice.
(Source: Wikipedia.)

The figure above clearly shows why (ω_1, ω_2) and (α_1, α_2) generate the same lattice, provided they satisfy the conditions outlined above. The blue parallelogram is the fundamental parallelogram with respect to the basis (ω_1, ω_2) , while the red one is the fundamental parallelogram with respect to the basis (α_1, α_2) . We know that $\alpha_1 = a\omega_1 + b\omega_2$ and $\alpha_2 = c\omega_1 + d\omega_2$. Now, let us look at the vectors ω_1 and ω_2 (Figure 6). For some arbitrary a , b , c and d (satisfying $ad - bc = 1$, of course), we can generate α_1 by stretching (multiplying) ω_1 by a factor of a and ω_2 by a factor of b , and taking the resultant sum of these two vectors. Since a and b are not necessarily equal, α_1 need not be along the same direction as the vector $\omega_1 + \omega_2$ (which is the special case of α_1 when $a = b = 1$). Similarly, we can generate α_2 from ω_1 and ω_2 using c and d . Now look at the red parallelogram (coordinates $0, \alpha_1, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2, \alpha_2$). If we take infinitely many parallel copies of α_1 and α_2 and extend them in both directions, we will end up with the exact same lattice that is generated by (ω_1, ω_2) , meaning

the lattice points will remain the same as in the case of (ω_1, ω_2) , and no points will be missed out.²⁰

2.3 The Fundamental Domain of the Modular Group

Let the lattice Λ be defined by ω_1 and ω_2 . Let us define $z = \omega_2/\omega_1$. We can choose ω_1 and ω_2 in a way that z lies in a special, restricted region called the **fundamental domain** (or fundamental region). This means if $z = \omega_2/\omega_1$ does not lie inside the fundamental domain, there always exists an element of the modular group that maps the lattice with basis (ω_1, ω_2) to another basis (α_1, α_2) such that $z' = \alpha_2/\alpha_1$ lies in the fundamental domain. Note that this element cannot be the 2×2 identity matrix; since the identity transformation takes us back to the same point, it cannot map a point outside the fundamental domain to a point inside the fundamental domain.

There are many possible fundamental domains for the action of a group on a set. Here, we are interested in the action of the modular group Γ on the set of all the points lying in the upper half complex plane H . A great choice of the fundamental domain in this case is the set D , which is composed of a set U plus a part of the boundary of U , where we define U as:

$$U = \{z \in H: |z| > 1, |Re(z)| < 1/2\}$$

where H is the upper half of the complex plane. The condition $z \in H$, which is equivalent to saying $Im(z) > 0$, ensures that z remains confined within the upper half plane. The condition $|z| > 1$ defines the region in H exterior to the unit circle (circle with unit radius) centered at the origin. The condition $|Re(z)| < 1/2$, which translates to $-1/2 < Re(z) < 1/2$, ensures that the real component of z (which is plotted along the horizontal axis) lies within $(-1/2, 1/2)$. The fundamental domain D is then built by adding the boundary on the left plus half the arc on the bottom:

$$D = U \cup \{z \in H: |z| \geq 1, Re(z) = -1/2\} \\ \cup \{z \in H: |z| = 1, -1/2 \leq Re(z) \leq 0\}$$

The conditions $|z| \geq 1$ and $Re(z) = -1/2$ in the second set correspond to the vertical left boundary of U (the vertical red line in Figure 7), while the conditions $|z| = 1$ and $-1/2 \leq Re(z) \leq 0$ correspond to the portion of the boundary of the

²⁰ A lattice is *fully* described by its points and their periodic arrangement; so as long as the points remain the same in both cases, we can say that the lattices generated in both cases are the same, even though the points are joined differently in the two cases due to the basis vectors being different. Also note that in a lattice, described by any fundamental pair of complex numbers, each and every lattice point must always lie on an intersection point of the two basis vectors, which are formed by the two complex numbers.

unit circle outlined in red in Figure 7. We could also have taken U plus the right boundaries (in the first quadrant) to be the fundamental domain.²¹

Figure 7: The fundamental domain of the modular group is the region shaded gray, plus the boundaries outlined in red. (Source: Wikipedia.)

All the points on the straight line in red in the second quadrant can be mapped to the corresponding points on the vertical boundary of U in the first quadrant by the matrix T , which along with the matrix S , are the generators of the modular group. Similarly, all the points on the red curve in the second quadrant can be mapped to the corresponding points on its counterpart in the first quadrant by the matrix S . So we only include one of these sets of points (the red curves) inside the fundamental domain. Thus, the complete fundamental domain D is the area shaded in gray plus the two red curves, as shown in Figure 7, where the horizontal axis represents $Re(z)$ and the vertical axis represents $Im(z)$. Each point in the upper half plane H outside the fundamental domain can be mapped inside the fundamental domain D by a modular transformation; however, no two points in the interior of D are linked by any modular transformation (that's how the fundamental domain D is defined). A point in H (outside D) can be mapped to a unique point in D by a unique matrix belonging to the modular group Γ , which is obviously not the 2×2 identity matrix.²² This means, for a given point z in H , there exists some matrix $A \in \Gamma$, such that $Az \in D$.

Note that any combination of S or T raised to certain integer powers, satisfying $S^4 = I$, $S^2 = (ST)^3$, where S and T are the generator matrices of the modular groups and I is the identity matrix of order 2, is a valid modular transformation (although obviously not all of these transformations can map a point outside the

²¹ In that case, we do not include the left boundaries, shown in red, inside the fundamental domain. To avoid redundancy, we only consider either the boundary in the first quadrant, or in the second quadrant, but not both. This ensures that the defining conditions of the fundamental domain are satisfied by all the points belonging to the fundamental domain.

²² The identity matrix maps the point to itself and hence is a trivial transformation. Multiplying a point outside the fundamental domain D with the identity matrix takes us back to the point itself, which lies outside D .

fundamental domain to a point inside the fundamental domain), and the set of all possible such combinations form the modular group (which is the group of all possible modular transformations). Since the matrices S and T generate the modular groups, these are the two fundamental transformations that define the modular group. Now, for the first kind of transformations, or the T transformations, the transformation matrix T is defined as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Integer powers of T , or T^n , where n is a positive or negative integer, has the general form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & n \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The basis of a lattice given by $(z, 1)$ can be expressed as a column vector:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us now left-multiply this column matrix with T (T^n with $n = 1$):

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} z + 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This new column matrix represents $(z + 1, 1)$. This transformation $z \rightarrow z + 1$ tells us that the lattice described by z is equivalent to the lattice described by $z + 1$; in other words, the lattice remains invariant under this transformation. z and $z + 1$ generate the same lattice Λ under this transformation, since the matrix T belongs to the modular group. Now, if we define $z' = z + 1$, under the transformation $z' \rightarrow z' + 1$ (transformation matrix T), $z' + 1$ will again generate the same lattice as z' , which in turn generates the same lattice as z . This means the lattices described by $z' + 1$ (which is $z + 1 + 1$ or $z + 2$) and z are the same, and so on.

Figure 8: Translation by the T matrix. (Source: Wikipedia.)

The figure above shows a T transformation $\tau \rightarrow \tau + 1$. The white parallelograms are the fundamental parallelograms formed by the basis $(\tau, 1)$. The fundamental parallelogram shaded in gray is formed by the basis $(\tau + 1, 1)$, which generates the same lattice. Essentially, the point τ has been translated to the right by 1 unit, and thus the vector joining τ to the origin has been replaced by the vector joining $\tau + 1$ to the origin.

The second kind of transformations are called S transformations²³, and in this case the transformation matrix S is defined as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

If we left-multiply the basis of a lattice given by $(z, 1)$, expressed as a column vector as before, with the matrix S , we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

This transformation $z \rightarrow -1/z$ tells us that the lattice generated by z is equivalent to the lattice generated by $-1/z$, since the matrix S belongs to the modular group.

S transformations are essentially conformal mappings on the complex plane, and are difficult to visualize. We can get a rough idea of S transformations by considering an arbitrary complex number $z = a + ib$, expressing $-1/z$ in the form of $u + iv$ (where u and v are functions of a and b), plotting some test points on the u - v complex plane and guessing the approximate shape of the transformed curve on the u - v plane by joining these points. Also, we must keep in mind the condition that z must belong to the upper half plane H .

We know that the S and T transformations generate the modular group. We can verify that, for the matrices S and T as defined above, $S^4 = I$ and $S^2 = (ST)^3$, where I is the 2×2 identity matrix. Now, to make sure that the modular group acts faithfully²⁴ on the upper half plane H , we define the projective special linear group $PSL(2, Z)$ as the modular group, and *not* $SL(2, Z)$. $SL(2, Z)$ is the full modular group, but it does not act faithfully on H . This distinction is important, because we define the fundamental domain with respect to $PSL(2, Z)$. Clearly, the 2×2 identity matrix I is the identity element of the group $SL(2, Z)$, since for any $A \in SL(2, Z)$, $AX = XA = A$ holds true iff $X = I$. Although for some particular matrix $A \in SL(2, Z)$, $AX = XA = A$ may be true even if $X \neq I$, we can call X the identity element of $SL(2, Z)$ only if this equation holds true for *all* $A \in$

²³ Since $S^2 = -I$, and $S^4 = (S^2)^2 = (-I)^2 = I$, we see that $S^3 = -S$, $S^5 = S$, $S^6 = -I$, $S^7 = -S$, $S^8 = I$ and so on. Thus, as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (n is a positive integer), the result of any integer power of $S - S^n -$ will always be either S , $-I$, $-S$ or I . Even if we consider negative integers, the set of all possible values of S^n is still finite.

²⁴ The action of group G on the set S is faithful iff $g * s = s$ inevitably implies $g = e$. For no other $g \neq e$ can $g * s$ be equal to s .

$SL(2, Z)$. And note that the identity element of a group is unique, meaning $SL(2, Z)$ can have only one identity element, and it is I . Now, why is the action of $PSL(2, Z)$ on H faithful, but not that of $SL(2, Z)$? Consider $-I$, the negative of the 2×2 identity matrix. Clearly, $-I \in SL(2, Z)$. Now consider the complex number $z = 1 + i$, $z \in H$. Multiplying $-I$ with the column matrix representing z , we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 - i \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get $(-1 - i)/-1$, which is the same as $-(-1 - i)$, or $1 + i = z$. Thus, $(-I) * z = z$. For the action of the group $SL(2, Z)$ to be faithful on H , $(-I) * z = z$ must imply that $-I$ is the identity element of $SL(2, Z)$, which is not true (the identity element is I). This single counterexample is enough to prove that the action of $SL(2, Z)$ on H is not faithful.

$PSL(2, Z)$ is defined as the quotient group $SL(2, Z)/\{I, -I\}$. This means we multiply each element of $SL(2, Z)$ with I , and then with $-I$, and $PSL(2, Z)$ is the group containing all these elements.²⁵ Consider a matrix A , such that A as well as $-A$ belongs to $SL(2, Z)$. This is possible, since $ad - bc = (-a)(-d) - (-b)(-c)$, which is one. Now, both $(-I)A$ and $I(-A)$ are elements of $PSL(2, Z)$, but since they represent the same matrix, essentially the matrices A and $-A$ in $SL(2, Z)$ are treated to be equivalent in $PSL(2, Z)$.²⁶ This means I and $-I$ are also equivalent matrices in $PSL(2, Z)$. In fact, we can prove that $A * z = z$, $A \in PSL(2, Z)$, $z \in H$, iff $A = I$, which is the identity element of $PSL(2, Z)$ in addition to $SL(2, Z)$. Thus, the action of $PSL(2, Z)$ on H is faithful.

2.4 Modular Transformations from H to D

The region D , as defined above, is the fundamental domain for the action of the modular group Γ on the upper half plane H by fractional linear transformations. The fundamental domain must satisfy the following conditions:

- For all $z \in H$, there exists some $A \in \Gamma$ satisfying $Az \in D$ (group operation is multiplication). And for a given $z \in H$, there is only one possible $A \in \Gamma$ such that $Az \in D$.
- Two points – both belonging inside the fundamental domain – can never be mapped from one to the other by some matrix A belonging to the modular group Γ .

²⁵ Of course, if we get an element more than once, we drop the duplicates and count it as a single element of the group.

²⁶ This is intuitively somewhat similar to how we treated diametrically opposite points on the surface of a sphere to be the same when constructing the projective space RP^2 .

- $Stab(z) = \{I\}$; $Az = z$ holds for all $z \in D$ iff $A = I$. However, for $z = i$ and $z = e^{2i\pi/3}$ (which are the **fixed points**), I is not the only stabilizer²⁷, meaning for these two values of z , $Az = z$ holds for I , as well as some $A \neq I$. No point, except these two fixed points, is mapped to itself by any matrix belonging to the modular group except the 2 X 2 identity matrix I .

First, let us discuss fixed points and why the three points mentioned above are fixed points. A fixed point or invariant point represents a value that does not change under a given transformation (in our case, a modular transformation). In other words, a fixed point maps to itself (under the appropriate modular transformation). For some point z inside the fundamental domain, and matrix A belonging to the modular group Γ , z is a fixed point under the transformation A iff $Az = z$. It is obvious that every point is a fixed point under the transformation A if A is the second order identity matrix I , since $Iz = z$ is always true. This is clearly a trivial case. Other than that, $z = i$ is a fixed point under the transformation S which, as we have already seen, belongs to the modular group. S is called a stabilizer of i – denoted $Stab(i)$ – since the point $z = i$ remains stable or fixed under the S transformation. We can verify this by pre-multiplying the 2 X 1 column matrix representing the point $z = i$ (the column matrix with its upper element i and lower element 1) by the matrix S :

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ i \end{pmatrix}$$

The result of the above matrix product essentially translates to $-1/i$, which is i (using $-1 = i^2$). In other words, $Si = i$.

One more fixed point, this one for the matrix ST , is the point $z = e^{i2\pi/3}$, which can also be written $(-1/2) + i(\sqrt{3}/2)$. If we plot the point $(-1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$ on the complex plane, we see that it belongs to the fundamental domain D ; it is the vertex of D at the intersection of the red curve and the red vertical line (Figure 7). Finding the product of the matrices ST and pre-multiplying with $z = e^{i2\pi/3} = (-1 + \sqrt{3}i)/2$, we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 + \sqrt{3}i \\ 2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 + \sqrt{3}i \\ 2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -2 \\ 1 + \sqrt{3}i \end{pmatrix}$$

So we get $-2/(1 + \sqrt{3}i)$, which on rationalization, translates to the original point $(-1 + \sqrt{3}i)/2$. Clearly, the fixed points $z = i$ and $z = e^{i2\pi/3}$ lie on the boundary of the fundamental domain and not in the interior U .

²⁷ Stabilizers are those elements of a group that do not change a particular point (or set of points) under the group action.

Now, to guess the general form of the matrix A such that A corresponds to a fixed point transformation for some point $z \in D$, we can start by setting $Im(Az) = Im(z)$, since $Az = z$.²⁸

Let us assume $z = x + iy$, which means $Im(z) = y$. Also, we have:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

where $ad - bc = 1$.

Let us now evaluate Az :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x + iy \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ax + b + iay \\ cx + d + icy \end{pmatrix}$$

On rationalization, and using $y = Im(z)$ and $ad - bc = 1$, we get:

$$Im(Az) = \frac{Im(z)}{|cz + d|^2}$$

For z to be a fixed point under A , $Im(Az) = Im(z)$, which yields $|cz + d|^2 = 1$. This represents the circle with radius $1/|c|$, and center on the horizontal axis, at the point $(-d/c, 0)$; hence z must lie on the circumference of this circle. For z to also lie inside the fundamental domain D , clearly the radius of the circle must be greater than or equal to 1; $1/|c| \geq 1$, or $|c| \leq 1$. This means c can be 0, 1 or -1 (c is an integer). Consider $c = \pm 1$. Under this condition, the center of the circle becomes $(\pm d, 0)$. For the circumference of the circle to at least touch the fundamental domain D , d must lie between -1 and $+1$ (meaning d is either 0, 1 or -1 , since d is an integer), because if the center of the circle (radius 1, since $c = \pm 1$) is at any point beyond this range, the circumference of the circle will never touch the fundamental domain D , meaning $z \notin D$. Thus, for $c = \pm 1$, $d = 0$ or ± 1 . Keeping all these in mind, let us fix $c = 1$ and $d = 0$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, the choice of a is arbitrary, as long as a is an integer. However, to satisfy $ad - bc = 1$, b must be -1 . For $a = 0$, the above matrix is S , under which $z = i$ is a fixed point. Note that the point $z = i$ belongs to the fundamental domain D . Now, let us set $c = 1$ and $d = 1$; we get a matrix of the form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & a - 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

²⁸ If Az and z are to represent the same point in D on the complex plane, their imaginary parts (the coordinate along the vertical axis) must be the same, as well as their real parts.

Here also the choice of a is arbitrary as long as a is an integer, but to satisfy $ad - bc = 1$, b must be $a - 1$. For $a = 0$, the above matrix is ST , under which $z = e^{2i\pi/3} \in D$ is a fixed point.

Next, we will prove that for some point $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$ (we ignore the trivial case of the transformation of some $z \in D$ to itself by the identity matrix), we can always find some matrix A belonging to the modular group, such that the point Az belongs to D .

Since A is a matrix belonging to the modular group, it is a product of certain integer powers of the generator matrices S and T . We take a point in H outside the fundamental domain D and subject it to a combination of appropriate S and T transformations until it is mapped to the fundamental domain D . For example, $z = 1 + 0.5i \in H$ is mapped to $z' = 2i \in D$, under the transformation ST^{-1} , and $z = 1.3 + 0.6i \in H$ is mapped to $z' = 0.34 + 1.34i \in D$, under the transformation TST^{-1} . It can easily be verified that the matrices ST^{-1} and TST^{-1} belong to the modular group (they have integer elements and determinant one). We will now prove that for every $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$, there must exist some $A \in \Gamma$ which maps z to some point belonging to the fundamental domain D (in other words, for $Az = z'$, $z' \in D$). Let $z = x + iy$, $z \in H$. Clearly $Re(z) = x$ and $Im(z) = y$. Let $A \in \Gamma$ be:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

where $ad - bc = 1$. And we also have:

$$Az = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x + iy \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ax + b + iay \\ cx + d + icy \end{pmatrix}$$

As we have seen previously, the imaginary part of Az is:

$$Im(Az) = \frac{Im(z)}{|cz + d|^2}$$

Clearly, $Im(Az) > 0$, since $Im(z) > 0$ ($z \in H$) and $|cz + d|^2$ is always positive. Now, $cz + d$ must be on the lattice generated by z and 1 . This means the distance of the point $cz + d$ from the origin, which is given by $|cz + d|$, must, by construction, be greater than or equal to either $|\pm z + 0|$, $|\pm z \pm 1|$ or $|0 \pm 1|$. Otherwise, the point $cz + d$ will lie inside the fundamental parallelogram generated by z and 1 , which would contradict the fact that $cz + d$ must lie on the lattice generated by z and 1 . The points $(\pm z, 0)$, $(\pm z, \pm 1)$ and $(0, \pm 1)$ are the vertices (except the origin) of the fundamental parallelogram²⁹ generated by z and 1 ; hence the possible points for $cz + d$ closest to the origin are these, which is

²⁹ Note that we use the \pm symbols because with respect to some origin $(0,0)$, the fundamental parallelograms generated by $(z, 1)$, $(z, -1)$, $(-z, 1)$ and $(-z, -1)$ are the same.

why $|cz + d|$ cannot be smaller than $|\pm z + 0|$, $|\pm z \pm 1|$ or $|0 \pm 1|$. Essentially, for $|cz + d|$, we have considered the cases $c = \pm 1, d = 0$; $c = \pm 1, d = \pm 1$ and finally $c = 0, d = \pm 1$. We can define possible matrices $A \in \Gamma$ for these combinations of c and d (the constraints on a and b can be obtained from $ad - bc = 1$), represent z as a column matrix, and verify that for $Az = z'$, the lattice generated by z' is the same one that is generated by z . We can of course generate this same lattice using different combinations of c and d , but in all of these cases, $|cz + d|$ will be greater than $|\pm z + 0|$, $|\pm z \pm 1|$ or $|0 \pm 1|$. Let us now look at the set $\{|\pm z + 0|, |\pm z \pm 1|, |0 \pm 1|\}$. Clearly this is a finite set, meaning we can find its minimum (the smallest element of the set) for a given z . And the value of $Im(Az)$ corresponding to the minimum value of $|cz + d|$ will be maximum, since $Im(Az) = Im(z)/|cz + d|^2$. Thus, for a given z , using the values of c and d for which $|cz + d|$ is minimum, and finding suitable a and b such that $ad - bc = 1$, we can find some matrix A belonging to the modular group such that $Im(Az)$ is maximum. Next, we find a suitable n (n is an integer), such that $T^n(Az) = z' \in \{H \mid -1/2 \leq Re(z') \leq 1/2\}$. Note that the matrix T^n , for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & n \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

T^1 , or just T , translates a point to the right by 1 unit; T^{-1} translates a point to the left by 1 unit; T^2 shifts a point to the right by 2 units; T^{-2} translates a point to the left by 2 units and so on. In general, T^n shifts a point to the right by n units, whereas T^{-n} shifts a point to the left by n units. Obviously, the matrix T^n also belongs to the modular group.

It is clearly possible to bring any point $Az \in H$ and $Az \notin D$ to some point $z' \in \{H \mid -1/2 \leq Re(z') \leq 1/2\}$ under the transformation T^n , for some suitable integer n . We are essentially shifting Az horizontally (left or right, depending on the initial position of Az), until we can bring the horizontal component of Az between $-1/2$ and $1/2$ (no constraints on the vertical component of Az). Now, let $T^n A = A'$. Since $A \in \Gamma$, A can be expressed as some product of integer powers of S and T . Clearly $T^n A = A'$ also belongs to Γ . Also, $Im(Az) = Im(A'z)$, which can be easily verified by multiplying the matrix $A' = T^n A$ with the column matrix representing z , and determining its imaginary part.³⁰ Thus, if we have chosen A and z such that $Im(Az)$ is maximum, then for the same A and z , $Im(A'z)$ would also be maximum, where $A' = T^n A$. Now, for $A' = T^n A$, we claim that any point $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$ is mapped inside the fundamental domain D by A' ; in other words, $A'z \in D$. If we can prove this claim, we prove that for every $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$, there must exist some matrix belonging to the modular group Γ which maps z to some point belonging to the fundamental domain D . Let us assume the

³⁰ The T transformation simply shifts a point horizontally, leaving its vertical coordinate untouched. This is why T transformations do not affect the imaginary part, just the real part.

claim that for $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$, $A'z \in D$ is false. Since $Re(z') = Re(A'z)$ already lies between $-1/2$ and $1/2$, for $A'z$ to *not* belong to the fundamental domain D , $A'z$ must lie inside the unit circle centered at the origin. In other words, $|A'z| < 1$. Now, if $A' \in \Gamma$, $SA' \in \Gamma$. And for the generator matrix S , $c = 1$ and $d = 0$. Thus, for the transformation $SA'z$, building on:

$$Im(Az) = \frac{Im(z)}{|cz + d|^2}$$

and using $c = 1$ and $d = 0$, we can write:

$$Im(S(A'z)) = \frac{Im(A'z)}{|A'z|^2}$$

Now, since $|A'z| < 1$, $1/|A'z|^2 > 1$, meaning $Im(A'z)/|A'z|^2 > Im(A'z)$. But this means $Im(SA'z) > Im(A'z)$, which is a contradiction since we chose A' and z such that $Im(A'z)$ is the maximum.³¹ Thus, the claim $|A'z| < 1$ must be incorrect, meaning $A'z$ lies within the fundamental domain D .

Now, our next claim is that for a given $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$ (again, we ignore the trivial case of transformations by the identity matrix), there is only one possible $A \in \Gamma$ such that $Az \in D$. Let us assume this is *not* true. This means for some z in H and $z \notin D$, and for $A_1, A_2 \in \Gamma$, $z_1, z_2 \in D$ and $z_1 \neq z_2$, $z_1 = A_1z$ and $z_2 = A_2z$. This means $z = A_1^{-1}z_1$ and also $z = A_2^{-1}z_2$. Equating them, we get $A_1^{-1}z_1 = A_2^{-1}z_2$, or $z_2 = A_2A_1^{-1}z_1$. It can easily be verified that if $A \in \Gamma$, then the inverse matrix $A^{-1} \in \Gamma$ as well. Thus, since $A_1 \in \Gamma$, $A_1^{-1} \in \Gamma$. And since $A_2 \in \Gamma$ as well, the product $A_2A_1^{-1} = A_3$ also belongs to the modular group Γ .³² This means $z_2 = A_3z_1$, $A_3 \in \Gamma$, which clearly violates the claim that we will prove next: no two points z_1, z_2 ($z_1 \neq z_2$) in the fundamental domain D satisfy $z_2 = Az_1$, for some $A \in \Gamma$. So for a given $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$, there is only one possible $A \in \Gamma$ such that $Az \in D$.

Let us now prove that no two points z_1, z_2 ($z_1 \neq z_2$) in D satisfy $z_2 = Az_1$, for some $A \in \Gamma$. First, we start by assuming $z_1, z_2 \in D$. Without loss of generality, we assume $Im(z_2) \geq Im(z_1)$. Now we assume $z_2 = Az_1$, where the matrix $A \in \Gamma$ is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

Clearly, $Im(z_2) = Im(Az_1) = Im(z_1)/|cz_1 + d|^2 \geq Im(z_1)$. Now, we see that $Im(z_1)/|cz_1 + d|^2 \geq Im(z_1)$ reduces to $|cz_1 + d|^2 \leq 1$. This region is the

³¹ We are doing the entire analysis for a particular A and z , but the proof is general since the choices of A and z are arbitrary as long as $A \in \Gamma$, $z \in H$ and $z \notin D$.

³² The group operation here is matrix multiplication, and since a group must satisfy the closure property, the product of two matrices belonging to the modular group must also belong to the modular group.

interior plus boundary of the circle centered at $(-d/c, 0)$ and with radius $1/|c|$. Since $z_1 \in D$, the radius of the circle $1/|c|$ must be greater than or at least equal to one, which means $|c| \leq 1$. Since c is an integer, this leaves us with three possible values of c : 0, 1 and -1 . First, let us fix $c = 0$. This reduces $|cz_1 + d|^2 \leq 1$ to $|d|^2 \leq 1$, which means d is either 0, 1 or -1 . Now, $c = 0$ and $ad - bc = 1$ means $ad = 1$. So if $d = 1$, $a = 1$; and if $d = -1$, $a = -1$. Clearly, d cannot be zero (else $ad - bc$ will not be one, since we've fixed $c = 0$). There is no restriction on b , except that b must be an integer. Thus, in this case, the general form of A is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \pm 1 & b \\ 0 & \pm 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Fixing $a = d = 1$, the above matrix is T^b . For $A = T^b$, since $z_1 \in D$, $Az_1 \in D$ holds true iff b is 0. For other values of b , T^b shifts z_1 left or right by 1 unit or more. Since the width of the fundamental domain D is 1 unit, and only the boundaries of U (the interior of D) in the second quadrant (and not the boundaries in the first quadrant) are part of the fundamental domain D , no translation of $z_1 \in D$ by 1 unit or more can bring it to a point in D , even if z_1 lies on the vertical boundary of D in the second quadrant. Thus, b must be 0. For $b = 0$, A is the identity matrix, and $Az_1 = z_1$. Since we assumed $Az_1 = z_2$ and $z_1 \neq z_2$, this is a contradiction ($Az_1 = z_1$ implies $z_2 = z_1$).

Now, let us consider the case where $c = \pm 1$ and $d = 0$. In this case, $|cz_1 + d|^2 \leq 1$ reduces to $|\pm z_1|^2 \leq 1$ or $|z_1| \leq 1$, which is the interior plus boundary of the unit circle centered at the origin. Clearly, for z_1 to satisfy $|z_1| \leq 1$ plus belong to D , z_1 must lie *on* the curved boundary of U in the second quadrant. Clearly, no matrix $A \in \Gamma$ can transform any such point to another point in D . A simple S transformation will map z_1 to the corresponding 'mirror-image' point on the curved boundary of U in the first quadrant, which is not a part of the fundamental domain D . And T transformations will be of no help either, and the same goes for any combination of different powers of S and T .

Now let us consider the case where $c = d = \pm 1$ (in other words, $c = d = 1$ or $c = d = -1$). In this case, $|cz_1 + d|^2 \leq 1$ reduces to $|z_1 + 1| \leq 1$. This region is the interior plus boundary of the unit circle centered at $(-1, 0)$. Clearly, this circle has only one point in common with D , which is $e^{2i\pi/3}$ and which clearly lies on the boundary of U (it is a part of D because it is in the second quadrant). Again, it is clear that there can be no $A \in \Gamma$ that can transform any such point to another point in D .

Finally, if we take the case where $c = -d = \pm 1$ (in other words, $c = 1$ and $d = -1$ or $c = -1$ and $d = 1$), $|cz_1 + d|^2 \leq 1$ reduces to $|z_1 - 1| \leq 1$. This region is the interior plus boundary of the unit circle centered at $(1, 0)$. In this case, the circle has no point in common with the fundamental domain D , which contradicts

the initial assumption that $z_1 \in D$. This proves that no two points z_1, z_2 ($z_1 \neq z_2$) in D satisfy $z_2 = Az_1$, for some matrix $A \in \Gamma$.

Thus, we have proved all the properties of the fundamental domain of the modular group D , and now we can say that:

$$D = U \cup \{z \in H: |z| \geq 1, \operatorname{Re}(z) = -1/2\} \\ \cup \{z \in H: |z| = 1, -1/2 \leq \operatorname{Re}(z) \leq 0\}$$

is a fundamental domain for the action of the modular group Γ on the upper half plane H by fractional linear transformations, since we have proved that it satisfies all the three defining properties of a fundamental domain.

3 Visualizing Modular Transformations from H to D

3.1 Map of the Lattice $\Lambda(0.5, 0.5i)$ inside the Fundamental Domain

Let us consider the lattice $\Lambda(0.5, 0.5i)$ on the complex plane. Also, assume we are in the upper half plane. Clearly, this lattice is the collection of all the points in the upper half plane that are 0.5 units away from its immediate neighbors on all sides. In the figure below, the horizontal axis represents the real axis; the vertical axis the imaginary one. The fundamental domain is the region enclosed by the red and black curves, plus just the red curves. The blue points represent the lattice $\Lambda(0.5, 0.5i)$. Of course, the lattice points extend infinitely leftward, rightward and upward. In the figure, we have only shown the points within the region enclosed by $[-3, 3]$ along the horizontal axis and $[0, 2]$ along the vertical axis.

Figure 9: The lattice $\Lambda(0.5, 0.5i)$ on the upper half complex plane H . (Generated using Desmos.)

Now, of course it is possible to find a matrix belonging to the modular group for each of these blue points that transforms that point to a point in the fundamental domain. Let us call this matrix A . Since the case above is extremely simple, we can easily divide the blue points into some regions and for each region, come up with a general form of the matrix that would transform the points in that region to some point in the fundamental domain. First, let us consider all the blue points *except* those whose coordinate on the vertical axis (say, y) is 0.5 (Category 1 points). We further divide this set of points into two subcategories: those points whose coordinates on the horizontal axis (say, x) are integers ($\dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$), say Category 1a points, and those points whose coordinates on the horizontal axis are not integers ($\dots, -2.5, -1.5, -0.5, 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, \dots$), say Category 1b points. For the first set of points (Category 1a), the matrix $A \in \Gamma$ that

transforms these points to points in the fundamental domain has the general form $A = T^{-x}$, where T is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and x is the coordinate of the point on the horizontal axis. Clearly, T^{-x} belongs to the modular group, since T is one of the generators of the modular group, and x is an integer for Category 1a points.

For Category 1b points, $A = T^{-[x]-1}$, where T is the same matrix as above, x is again the coordinate of the point on the horizontal axis, and $[x]$ represents the greatest integer function of x ; $[x]$ is simply the *greatest* integer that is *smaller* than x .³³ Now, let us call the remaining points (the points with $y = 0.5$) as Category 2 points. Now, let us call all category 2 points with $x < 0$ (all the Category 2 points lying on the second quadrant) as Category 2a points, and the rest ($x > 0$) as Category 2b points. For Category 2a points, $A = T^{[x]+[-x]}S^1T^{-[x]}$ and for Category 2b points, $A = T^{-[x]-[-x]}S^1T^{-[x]}$, where S and T are the generators of the modular groups, x is the coordinate of the point on the horizontal axis, $[x]$ is the greatest integer function of x , $[-x]$ is the greatest integer function of $-x$. If x is an integer, we see that both $A = T^{[x]+[-x]}S^1T^{-[x]}$ and $A = T^{-[x]-[-x]}S^1T^{-[x]}$ reduces to $A = S^1T^{-x}$. So when x is an integer, the matrix S^1T^{-x} transforms both Category 2a and Category 2b points to points in the fundamental domain. And if x is not an integer, for Category 2a points, $A = T^{-1}S^1T^{-[x]}$ and for Category 2b points, $A = T^1S^1T^{-[x]}$.

It should be noted that more than one blue point can get mapped to the same point in the fundamental domain, under the corresponding matrices. For example, consider the point $-3 + i$. It has the coordinates $(-3,1)$, and clearly it is a Category 1a point. Thus, for this point $A = T^{-x} = T^3$. If we multiply T^3 with this point, we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -3 + i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We see that the transformed point is i , and it has the coordinates $(0,1)$, which clearly belongs to the fundamental domain. Now consider the Category 2b point $2.5 + 0.5i$, with coordinates $(2.5,0.5)$. In this case, we have $A = T^{-[x]-[-x]}S^1T^{-[x]} = T^1S^1T^{-2}$. If we multiply $T^1S^1T^{-2}$ with this point, we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2.5 + 0.5i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -3 \\ 1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2.5 + 0.5i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

³³ This modification was required because x is not an integer for Category 1b points. However, for the matrix T^n to belong to the modular group, n must be an integer. The greatest integer function is of great help in representing the general form of the matrix A when x is not an integer.

The transformed point is again i , thus demonstrating that more than one blue point can get mapped to the same point in the fundamental domain, under the action of corresponding matrices. This means, in loose terms, it is possible for the density of a mapped point in the fundamental domain to be more than that of a blue point, because a single mapped point in the fundamental domain can correspond to more than one blue point. In fact, *all* the blue points (that are shown in Figure 9) map to just six points inside the fundamental domain (the green points, Figure 10).

Figure 10: The map of all the points in the lattice $\Lambda(0.5,0.5i)$ in the fundamental domain D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Figure 11 below shows both the set of the original points in the upper half plane (the blue dots) as well as the set of the transformed points inside the fundamental domain (the green dots).

Figure 11: The map of all the points in the lattice $\Lambda(0.5,0.5i)$ in the fundamental domain D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Clearly, the set of transformed points belongs to the same lattice as the set of the blue points. Thus, for the lattice $\Lambda(0.5,0.5i)$, the transformation to the fundamental domain is symmetric under the modular group. This means that the set of all the blue points can be equivalently represented by the set of all the green points. The potential power of modular symmetry is evident from this; if we can show that a large number of points in H is symmetric under the modular group to a smaller set of points in D , we considerably simplify the problem. Assume the set of blue points represents different states of a real physical system. If we could reduce them to just six green points, it becomes much easier for us to study with the system.

3.2 Mapping Points in H with $y \geq 1$ inside the Fundamental Domain

The example of the lattice $\Lambda(0.5,0.5i)$ was relatively simple. We will now consider any general point outside the fundamental domain in the upper half plane H whose coordinate on the vertical axis is greater than or equal to 1 ($y \geq 1$). Let us further divide the region defined by these points into two smaller regions: Region 1, or the region containing points which have their coordinates on the real axis less than -0.5 ($x < -0.5$), and Region 2, or the region containing points which have their coordinates on the real axis greater than or equal to 0.5 ($x \geq 0.5$); remember that points with $x = 0.5$ do not belong to the fundamental domain, but points with $x = -0.5$ do, assuming $y \geq \sqrt{3}/2$. It can easily be verified that the matrix $T^{-[x]}$, where $[x]$ is the greatest integer function of x , transforms the points in Region 1 with $x \in (-n.5, -n - 1]$, where n is a positive integer, to points in the fundamental domain. For example, let us put $n = 3$. Any point with x satisfying $-3.5 < x \leq -4$ will be transformed to some point in the fundamental domain by the matrix $T^{-[-4]} = T^4$; the greatest integer function of any $x \in (-3.5, -4]$ is -4 . And the matrix $T^{-[x]-1}$ transforms all other points in Region 1 (points with x that does not satisfy $-n.5 < x \leq -n - 1$) to the fundamental domain. For Region 2, the matrix $T^{-[x]-1}$ transforms the points with $x \in [n.5, n + 1)$, where n is a positive integer, to points in the fundamental domain. For example, let us put $n = 1$. Any point with x satisfying $1.5 \leq x < 2$ will be transformed to some point in the fundamental domain by the matrix $T^{-[1]-1} = T^{-2}$; the greatest integer function of any $x \in [1.5, 2)$ is one. And the matrix $T^{-[x]}$ transforms all other points in Region 2 (points with x that does not satisfy $n.5 \leq x < n + 1$) to the fundamental domain. Let us confine ourselves between $y = 1.5$ and $y = 2$. We start with a random set of points (the green points in Figure 12) inside the square defined by the coordinates $(1,1.5)$, $(1.5,1.5)$, $(1.5,2)$ and $(1,2)$. Clearly, these points lie in Region 2. The transformed set of points in the fundamental domain (the blue points) lie in the square defined by the coordinates $(0,1.5)$, $(0.5,1.5)$, $(0.5,2)$ and $(0,2)$.

Figure 12: The green points in H maps to the blue points in D . (Generated using Desmos.³⁴)

Now, let us consider some more points (the purple points in Figure 13) lying on the edges of the first square (the square outside the fundamental domain). These points are transformed to the black points inside the fundamental domain. The points on the edge of the square with $x = 1$ are mapped to points inside the fundamental domain with $x = 0$; in other words, these points are just shifted to the left by 1 unit, like all the other points inside the square (the green points). However, the points on the edge of the square with $x = 1.5$ are mapped to points inside the fundamental domain with $x = -0.5$. These points are shifted to the left by 2 units, since points with $x = 0.5$ do not belong to the fundamental domain.

Figure 13: The purple points in H maps to the black points in D . (Generated using Desmos.)

³⁴ Henceforth, the boundaries of the fundamental domain have been colored randomly. It must be kept in mind that only the boundaries lying in the second quadrant belong to D .

Let us now consider the set of purple points, in Region 2, as shown in Figure 14. The transformed points are shown in black.

Figure 14: The square with the purple points in H maps to the square with the black points in D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Now, let us move to Region 1. Consider the mapping of the blue points to the green points in the fundamental domain (Figure 15).

Figure 15: The square with the blue points in H maps to the square with the green points in D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Now, let us shift the blue points in Figure 15 to the left by 1 unit and add some more points with $x = -1.5$ (in the previous case, we did not consider points with $x = -0.5$ since those points already belong to the fundamental domain). The mapped points in the fundamental domain (the green points) are the same as in

the previous case, plus the additional points with $x = -0.5$ corresponding to the points we added with $x = -1.5$ (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: The square with the blue points in H maps to the square with the green points in D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Now, let us shift the blue points above to the right by 0.5 units; this gives a new set of points (the purple points in Figure 17). The transformed points are shown in black.

Figure 17: The square with the purple points in H maps to the square with the black points in D . (Generated using Desmos.)

Note that the points inside the squares in the above example have been randomly chosen. This makes it clear that as we consider random points outside the

fundamental domain in the upper half plane H farther and farther to the left and right, *infinitely many* points in H will be mapped to the *same* point in D . For alternate squares of length 0.5 units in Regions 1 or 2 outside D , the mapped points will lie in either the corresponding square of length 0.5 units in the first quadrant or the same in the second quadrant in D . And in all the cases, the points in H with x coordinates of the form $n.5$, where n is a positive or negative integer, get mapped to the corresponding points in D with $x = -0.5$ and the same y . And for the points with x coordinates of the form n (n is a positive or negative integer), the mapped points in D have $x = 0$.

Figure 18: Modular transformations from H to D for points with $y \geq 1$. (Generated using Desmos.)

In the above figure, the blue points outside the fundamental domain in the alternate squares get mapped to the green points in the fundamental domain. All of the green points are in the square with coordinates $(0,1.5)$, $(1.5,1.5)$, $(1.5,2)$ and $(0,2)$, except the green points on $x = -0.5$, which correspond to the blue points with $x = n.5$ (n is a positive or negative integer). The black points outside the fundamental domain in alternate squares get mapped to the red points in the fundamental domain. If we consider all points in Regions 1 and 2, clearly the concentration of mapped points in D with $x = -0.5$ is higher than that for any other $x \in (-0.5,0.5)$. This is because of the ‘extra’ set of points outside the fundamental domain in Region 2 with $x = 0.5$, which maps to points in D with $x = -0.5$.

3.3 Mapping Points in H with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$ inside the Fundamental Domain

First, we divide all the points in H with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$ into three regions: Region 3 which contains all of the points with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$ and $-\infty < x < -1/2$, Region 4 which contains all of the points *outside the fundamental domain* with

$\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$ and $-1/2 < x < 1/2$ and Region 5 which contains all of the points with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y \leq 1$ and $1/2 \leq x < \infty$. All points in Region 4 are mapped to the fundamental domain by the matrix S . All points in Region 3 that can be brought inside the fundamental domain just by shifting them to the right by some integer unit (without displacing them vertically), follow the same rules as points in Region 1; they are mapped into the fundamental domain by $T^{-[x]}$ if $x \in (-n.5, -n - 1]$, where n is a positive integer, and by $T^{-[x]-1}$ otherwise. An example of such a point is $(-1.57, 0.93)$, because pre-multiplying this point with T^2 gives $(0.43, 0.93)$, which lies in the fundamental domain. For all other points in Region 3, depending on whether $x \in (-n.5, -n - 1]$, we just pre-multiply the above matrices with S . This means, the matrix $ST^{-[x]}$ transforms all points in Region 3 with $x \in (-n.5, -n - 1]$ to points inside the fundamental domain, and $ST^{-[x]-1}$ transforms all points in Region 3 with $x \notin (-n.5, -n - 1]$ to points inside the fundamental domain, as long as these points cannot be brought inside the fundamental domain just by shifting them to the right by some integer unit. And similarly, all points in Region 5 that can be brought inside the fundamental domain just by shifting them to the left by some integer unit, follow the same rules as points in Region 2; they are mapped into the fundamental domain by $T^{-[x]-1}$ if $x \in [n.5, n + 1)$, where n is a positive integer, and by $T^{-[x]}$ otherwise. For all other points in Region 3, depending on whether $x \in [n.5, n + 1)$, we again pre-multiply the above matrices with S . This means, the matrix $ST^{-[x]-1}$ transforms all points in Region 3 with $x \in [n.5, n + 1)$ to points inside the fundamental domain, and $ST^{-[x]}$ transforms all points in Region 3 with $x \notin [n.5, n + 1)$ to points inside the fundamental domain, as long as these points cannot be brought inside the fundamental domain just by shifting them to the right by some integer unit.

Figure 19: Modular transformations from H to D for points with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$. (Generated using Desmos.)

In the figure above (Figure 19), the red points, the blue points and the green points outside the fundamental domain belong to Region 3, Region 4 and Region 5

respectively. And the corresponding transformed points inside the fundamental domain have been shown in the same color as the original points.³⁵

All the points lying on the part of the circumference of the unit circle centered at origin in the first quadrant with $y \geq \sqrt{3}/2$ are mapped to points lying on the part of the circumference of this unit circle in the second quadrant with $y \geq \sqrt{3}/2$. Of course, the latter set of points belongs to the fundamental domain whereas the former set of points does not (the former set of points belong to Region 4). Now, all the points in Region 5 that can be mapped to any point in this former set of points by shifting them to the left by some integer units are also mapped to the latter set of points. And of course, there are the points in Region 3 that can be mapped to the latter set of points by shifting them to the right by some integer units. This clearly shows that the concentration of mapped points in the fundamental domain for Regions 3, 4 and 5 is higher for $x^2 + y^2 = 1, -1/2 < x < 0$ (the latter set of points, or the boundary of the fundamental domain in the second quadrant lying on the unit circle).

We also see that all points in Regions 3, 4 and 5 with $x = n.5$, where n is an integer, are mapped to the points inside the fundamental domain with $x = -0.5$ and $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$. Thus, the concentration of mapped points in the fundamental domain is also slightly higher for $x = -1/2, \sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$. Finally, all points in the Regions 3, 4 and 5 with $x = n$, where n is any integer, are mapped to certain points inside the fundamental domain with $x = 0$ (the imaginary axis). Along with all the negative and positive integers in Regions 3, 4 and 5 that can be horizontally shifted to their corresponding points with $x = 0$ in Region 4, these points ($x = 0$, Region 4) themselves are also mapped into points with $x = 0$ inside the fundamental domain (essentially shifted upward). Thus, the concentration of the mapped points in the fundamental domain with $x = 0$, for original points in Regions 3, 4 and 5 is also slightly higher than the surrounding points. Finally, it is clear that the concentration of transformed points will be higher near the bottom of the fundamental domain (and not just on the lower boundary in the second quadrant). This is because the transformed points inside the fundamental domain corresponding to the points in Region 4 – including all the points in Regions 3 and 5 that can be brought in Region 4 by an appropriate T transformation – overlap with some points inside the fundamental domain (with $y \geq 1$) which correspond to original points in Regions 1 and 2.

If we consider the mapping of any point in H with $y \geq 1$ inside the fundamental domain D and the mapping of any point in H with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$ inside D , we see that the same point in the fundamental domain D with $y \geq 1$ may correspond to more than one point in H (one belonging to the first set of points in H , in other words, those points in H with $y \geq 1$, and the other belonging to the second set of

³⁵ Not all transformed points are visible in Figure 19, since some of them overlap.

points in H with $\sqrt{3}/2 \leq y < 1$. This means if we transform all the points in H (and outside D) inside the fundamental domain D , the concentration of the mapped points in D will not be uniform. As we have discussed, we expect the concentration of points on the left vertical border as well as the points near the bottom of the fundamental domain to be maximum.

3.4 An Algorithm for $H \rightarrow D$ Transformations

We are now interested in developing an algorithm that would map any point in the upper half complex plane H inside the fundamental domain D . The best way to approach this is to divide the upper half complex plane H into different regions as shown in Figure 20. Inside each region, the matrix that transforms points to D belonging to that region is mentioned.

Figure 20: We divide the upper half plane H into appropriate regions, and apply unique transformations to each region to map them inside the fundamental domain D . (Source: Open Systems - Ark's Blog.)

As we move closer and closer to the horizontal axis, the upper half plane gets divided into more and more regions (overlapping semicircles). For each of these regions, a different combination of powers of S and T transforms points to some point inside the fundamental domain. For points inside the fundamental domain (shaded in gray), transformation by the second order identity matrix I_2 keeps the points inside the fundamental domain (I_2 transforms the points to themselves).

Now that we have divided the upper half plane H into different regions, we will next generate a large number of random, uniformly-distributed points in H

(outside D) and transform them inside the fundamental domain D . To do that, we need to define the transformations uniquely for each region. For simplicity, we leave out the points extremely close to the horizontal axis; we do not define the smaller semicircles extremely closest to the real axis in our code.

Next, we define the fundamental transformations S and T . The T transformation simply shifts a point in the horizontal direction by some integer amount, and is easy to define. For a point in H with coordinates (x, y) , T only has an effect on x , and not on y . The T transformation transforms the point (x, y) to a point (x', y') , where $x' = x + n$ (n is an integer), and $y' = y$. The S transformation, on the other hand, transforms a point (x, y) to a point (x', y') , where $x' = -x/(x^2 + y^2)$ and $y' = y/(x^2 + y^2)$.³⁶ Once we have defined S and T , we can specify the combination of S and T that transforms the points in H to some points in D , for each region. Through this code, we wish to verify whether the above transformations, in general, map any point in H (depending on the region) to a point inside D . Let us look at the output of the initial code (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Output of the initial code.³⁷

³⁶ This can be verified by pre-multiplying the column matrix with the upper element as $x + iy$ and the lower element as 1 by the S matrix. This column matrix represents the point (x, y) , where x is the real part and y is the imaginary part, and the column matrix we get after the multiplication represents the point (x', y') , where x' is the real part and y' is the imaginary part.

³⁷ The output was generated in Google Colab using Python 3. The code is given in Appendix 7.

In the above output, the light blue points are the original points in H (we have generated 20000 such points), and the green points are the transformed points. In the code, we have defined eleven regions in H – the regions corresponding to the transformation matrices T , T^{-1} , ST , S , ST^{-1} , $T^{-1}ST$, TST , $T^{-1}S$, TS , $T^{-1}ST^{-1}$ and TST^{-1} in Figure 20 – and transformed the points in these eleven regions to D using the corresponding transformation matrices.³⁸ Since points belonging to these eleven regions in H have their horizontal coordinates confined between -1.5 and 1.5 (see Figure 20), we have generated our original points in H with $-0.5 \leq x \leq 0.5$ only.

We see that very few green points lie outside the fundamental domain; most of the transformed points lie inside D . The few anomalous points are sure to correspond to original points lying very close to the horizontal axis (real axis), because we have not divided H into further regions close to the horizontal axis (see Figure 20). From the output, it is also clear that the density of the transformed points (green points) is maximum at the bottom of the fundamental domain. In our code, for the sake of simplicity, we have not separately excluded the boundaries of the fundamental domain (outlined in black) in the first quadrant; we have assumed the boundaries in both the first and second quadrants to be a part of D . Due to this, the expected higher concentration of points on the left boundary of D (as compared to the right boundary) is not apparent in the output. However, otherwise the code works reasonably well.

Now, let us modify our code and color the transformed points differently based on the region in H (out of the eleven regions we have defined) they originated in. This is being done to check the region(s) in H that the anomalous points (transformed points that lie outside the fundamental domain D) are originally from. Let us tabulate the color of the transformed points and the corresponding transformations.

<i>Color of transformed point</i>	<i>Corresponding transformation(s)</i>
Light green	T, T^{-1}
Green	ST, S, ST^{-1}
Yellow	$T^{-1}S, TS$
Purple	$TST, T^{-1}ST^{-1}$
Red	$T^{-1}ST, TST^{-1}$

Table 1: Assigning different colors to different groups of transformed points based on the corresponding $H \rightarrow D$ transformations.

³⁸ Note that the boundaries of the different regions in H have not been outlined in the output.

Let us now look at the output of this code (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Output of the modified code.³⁹

We see that the anomalous points are green, purple or red points, which corresponds to the regions defined by the transformations ST , S , ST^{-1} , TST , $T^{-1}ST^{-1}$, $T^{-1}ST$ and TST^{-1} . All of these regions lie close to the horizontal axis.

In both of the codes above, we have confined the vertical coordinates of the original points (colored light blue) to be greater than 0.3. This has been done to ensure no point in H is generated very close to the horizontal axis (which corresponds to very small values of the vertical coordinate). This partially compensates our not defining regions very close to the horizontal axis in our code. If we reduce the minimum allowed vertical coordinate for our original points slightly, the number of anomalous points would increase by a great amount. In the code that generated the output below (Figure 23), we have confined the vertical coordinates of the original points to be greater than 0.2 instead of 0.3; and clearly there is a significant increase in the number of anomalous points.

³⁹ See Appendix 7 for the code.

Notice that the anomalous points are, again, either green, or purple, or red. They seem to be arranged in a pattern, which means we need to add further S and/or T transformations to the transformations they have already been subject to, to ensure they map inside the fundamental domain D . In general, the closer we reach to the horizontal axis, the more complex the transformations that map the points lying there inside the fundamental domain. There are no anomalous points corresponding to the transformations T and T^{-1} , for instance; but there are anomalous points corresponding to more complex transformations (like TST , $T^{-1}ST^{-1}$, $T^{-1}ST$ and TST^{-1}).⁴⁰

Figure 23: The number of anomalous points increases if we let the original points lie closer to the horizontal axis. All anomalous points are green, purple or red.

Let us now run our code one more time, this time for a larger number of original points (30000 instead of 20000) and also, we will allow the original points to lie closer to the horizontal axis (their vertical coordinates need to be greater than 0.15 now). We expect to see a much higher number of anomalous points, and we also expect to see the pattern in which they are arranged more prominently.

⁴⁰ Notice that there is no anomaly seen for the yellow points, which correspond to the transformations $T^{-1}S$ and TS . The regions in H corresponding to these transformations lie directly below the fundamental domain (their horizontal coordinates lie between -0.5 and 0.5).

The output is shown in Figure 24. Although the original points have been generated with their horizontal coordinates lying between -1.5 and 1.5 , we see that the anomalous points corresponding to these original points extend beyond this region.

Figure 24: The number of anomalous points increases significantly and the anomalous points spread out, if we increase the number of original points generated and let them lie even closer to the horizontal axis.

It is noticeable that even now, the anomalous points are green, purple or red, and not of any other color. They seem to spread out in a pattern, but it does not seem to be a symmetric pattern. Also, notice that as we keep increasing the number of original points and allow them to lie closer to the horizontal axis, we observe that the transformed points (other than the light green ones) reach farther up the fundamental domain. Even though the density of transformed points is the maximum in the bottom region of the fundamental domain, if we take into consideration *all* the points lying extremely close to the horizontal axis, the density of transformed points in the upper regions would also increase.

Let us run our code one last time, this time for 50000 original points whose vertical coordinates need to be greater than 0.1. The output is shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: The anomalous points greatly increase in number and spread out as we further increase the number of original points generated, and let the original points lie even closer to the horizontal axis.

We see an even larger number of anomalous points spreading out much farther, but in a similar manner as previously observed. And once again, all the anomalous points are green, purple or yellow. The transformed points except light green reach even higher within the fundamental domain.

The above outputs confirm that our algorithm transforms points from H to D reasonably well, keeping in mind the approximations and eliminations made to simplify the code. For one, we did not distinguish between the boundaries of the fundamental domain D lying in the first and second quadrant. For another, we considered only eleven regions in H . And of course, we did not consider the points in H that lie very close to the horizontal axis.

Conclusion

In this report, we have explored the modular group and its fundamental domain. We have investigated the nature of transformations of points belonging to the upper half complex plane (outside the fundamental domain) to points inside the fundamental domain of the modular group, both mathematically and computationally. Mathematically, we have looked at the modular group, its generators and its fundamental domain. We have rigorously proved how its fundamental domain is defined, and why. Then we have studied the different combinations of the matrices S and T – which are the generators of the modular group – that transform points belonging to different regions in the upper half plane to points inside the fundamental domain. We have further developed a general algorithm for these transformations and within the limits allowed by the approximations in our code, verified it in different ways for eleven regions in the upper half plane.

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Appendix 1: Noether's Theorem, Symmetry and Symmetry Breaking

Symmetry plays a very important role in physics, and group theory is the mathematical framework we need to study various symmetries in physics. **Noether's theorem** claims that associated with every symmetry, there is a conserved quantity. Time symmetry, for instance, is associated with the conservation of energy. Time symmetry, in very simple terms, means that the laws of physics do not change with time. If we perform an experiment now and two days later, under exactly the same external conditions, we would not expect different results. This is because we implicitly assume time symmetry (the laws of physics would be the same two days from now as it is today).

Let us say we are interested in measuring the weight of an object, which is just the product of its mass and the acceleration due to gravity, both of which are constants at a fixed point in space. We do not expect the weight of the object to change with time, as long as we do not move the object. Let us assume this was not the case (in other words, assume there was no time symmetry). That implies it would take different amounts of energy to lift this object up at different points in time (even if the object is at the same point in space), since its weight changes with time. We would need to spend the least amount of energy if we lift the object up when its weight is minimum. However, if we keep track of the object's weight and drop the object from some height at a later time when its weight is higher than what it was when it was lifted, we would generate more energy from dropping the object than we had used to lift it. Clearly, this is a violation of the law of conservation of energy. This means energy cannot be conserved if there is no time symmetry. Of course, this is not a rigorous proof of the connection between time symmetry and the law of conservation of energy. However, it serves as an effective, qualitative illustration.

It is important to understand that symmetry not only refers to the symmetry of things, but also the symmetry of laws. By symmetry of laws, we mean that even if certain properties of the particles or fields change in a certain manner, the laws governing those particles or fields do not change. **Spontaneous symmetry breaking** plays a particularly important role in **quantum field theory**, which provides a mathematical framework for describing how elementary particles interact with one another and gives rise to the fundamental forces (except gravity, which is something that cannot be explained in the framework of quantum field theory). It is believed that the four fundamental forces we see today were unified in the early universe. The energy and temperature of the early universe were

extremely high. As the universe expanded and cooled down over time, the unified ‘superforce’ is thought to have separated into the distinct forces that we see today, due to spontaneous symmetry breaking. Let us try to understand the idea of spontaneous symmetry breaking, in simple terms. A very useful way to think of symmetries is by asking whether we can distinguish the system in different directions, different points in space or at different times. If we can, we say symmetry has been broken. We can break the symmetry of a system by changing its physical properties (**explicit symmetry breaking**), for instance, by distorting one side of an equilateral triangle. However, in spontaneous symmetry breaking, the symmetry is broken in a more subtle way. In the figure below, from the peak position the system appears the same in all directions, and the symmetry is unbroken. However, from the lower position, clearly the symmetry is broken, because the system does not appear the same if we look to the left and then to the right.

Figure 26: Illustration of spontaneous symmetry breaking. (Source: Condensed Concepts.)

Here is a good analogy. Say we are in a dilemma; we cannot decide whether to go with option A or option B. This means the symmetry between option A and option B is not broken; both options are equally appealing to us. What we often do in such situations is toss a coin, and associate heads with option A and tails with option B (say). Since we ourselves cannot decide between the two options, we make the outcome dependent on an outcome that is beyond our control. Before we toss the coin, both heads and tails are equally likely; but after we toss it, we get either heads or tails. You can think of it as spontaneous symmetry breaking; the symmetry between options A and B has been broken, even though the laws of

probability governing a coin toss has not changed. Of course, this is just an analogy, and not a rigorous illustration.

Spontaneous symmetry is broken spontaneously (as the name suggests) as the system evolves following the laws of physics, even though these laws do not change. Breaking of symmetry is, in general, essential for stability. As the universe cools down and attains a more stable configuration (as compared to the early universe configuration which was highly unstable), symmetry is spontaneously broken. Similarly, even in the process of gases cooling and condensing into liquids, and then liquids further solidifying into solids, the symmetry of the system decreases.

Solid has a crystalline structure, and it has **discrete translational symmetry**. We can move from any lattice point to any other lattice point, but we cannot end up at any other point within the structure (for instance, points on the edge of a unit cell except the vertices, or points in the interior of the cell). The symmetry associated with this structure is discrete because we are not allowed to move continuously within the structure, we can only occupy positions separated by a discrete distance. If we consider a hypothetical crystalline lattice that extends infinitely in all directions, it appears exactly the same everywhere, and from every lattice point, the structure would look the same in all directions as well. This shows that the structure is discretely symmetric; if we translate or shift between lattice points, the structure still appears the same. Now, let us consider a system of an infinite number of gas particles, extending infinitely in all directions. The gas particles are free, unlike atoms in a solid. Hence, they move about randomly, colliding with one another. This system possesses **continuous translational symmetry**; there is no restriction on the positions that the gas particles can occupy. The gas looks the same from *every* point within this infinite box of gas. If we are lost in this box filled with an infinite number of gas particles and extending away indefinitely in all directions, everything around us would appear exactly the same, regardless of where we are within the system, or which way we look. This shows why gas, in general, is more symmetric than solid, and that symmetry is broken as gases cool down to solids.

Appendix 2: Irreducible Fractions and Matrices of $SL(2, Z)$

Consider a matrix A belonging to the group $SL(2, Z)$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

The above matrix satisfies the condition $ad - bc = 1$, which implies that the fraction $(a + b)/(c + d)$ is irreducible, or that its greatest common divisor is one. Let us see why.

Let us assume $(a + b)/(c + d)$ is reducible, which means for coprime integers m and n , $a + b = mk$ and $c + d = nk$, where k is the greatest common divisor of $a + b$ and $c + d$. Rearranging $a + b = mk$, we get $b = mk - a$; and similarly $d = nk - c$. Substituting this in $ad - bc = 1$, we get $k(an - cm) = 1$, or $1/k = an - cm$. Since a, c, n and m are integers, $an - cm$ is also an integer, and for $1/k$ to be equal to an integer, k must be 1. This shows that the greatest common divisor of $a + b$ and $c + d$ is one, hence the fraction $(a + b)/(c + d)$ is irreducible.

Now, if p/q is another irreducible fraction, then the fraction $(ap + bq)/(cp + dq)$ is also irreducible. If we express the fraction p/q as a 2×1 column matrix, with p as the upper element and q as the lower element, and pre-multiply it with the matrix A , we get another 2×1 column matrix with its upper element $ap + bq$ and the other element $cp + dq$. This matrix represents the fraction $(ap + bq)/(cp + dq)$, which is irreducible; the action of the modular group on an irreducible fraction can never turn it into a reducible fraction. Thus, we can also conclude that for any pair of irreducible fractions – say, p/q and r/s – there exist integers a, b, c and d such that:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in SL(2, Z)$$

and $r = ap + bq$ and $s = cp + dq$.

Appendix 3: Modular Symmetry and the Torus

A **torus** is a surface of revolution generated by revolving a circle in three-dimensional space one full revolution about an axis that is coplanar with the circle. More simply, we can generate a torus by bending a flat two-dimensional surface into a cylindrical shape by connecting two parallel edges, and then connecting the other two edges, as shown below.

Figure 27: A torus can be constructed from a flat two-dimensional surface by joining its edges as shown. (Source: Sophia Potoczak Bragdon, ResearchGate.)

Clearly, there exists a flat representation of a torus. The flat two-dimensional surface is a complete representation of the torus; and points on this surface form a lattice which can be generated by many possible fundamental pairs linked by modular transformations. We have already seen how modular transformations provide a symmetry on a two-dimensional lattice; and hence the torus also exhibits modular symmetry.

The simplest example of a flat torus is the Cartesian plane under the identifications $(x, y) \sim (x + 1, y) \sim (x, y + 1)$, where \sim represents an equivalent relation. Intuitively, the points of each equivalence class are identified or “glued together” for forming a new topological space.

For example, the topological sphere is essentially the quotient space of a disk, and it can be constructed by joining all diametrically-opposite points lying on the circumference of the disk. In our case, folding a rectangle ABCD into a cylinder about an axis parallel to the sides AB and CD corresponds to joining the points on side AB with the corresponding points on side CD – the points on CD lying

on the normal drawn from their counterparts on AB. This transformation also transforms the sides AD and BC to circles, although we have not joined them yet. Now if we connect the ends of this cylinder, we essentially join all the points on AD with the corresponding points on BC, and now we have constructed a torus. Of special interest in the study of modular forms is the complex torus, which is defined as the quotient group V/Λ , where Λ is a lattice in a vector space V isomorphic to C^n (n is the dimension of the complex space; $C^n = C \times C \times \dots \times C$, n times), the n -fold Cartesian product of the complex plane C with itself.

Appendix 4: Möbius Transformations

The modular group is a subgroup of a bigger group: the **Möbius group**. A **Möbius transformation** of the complex plane is a bijective⁴¹, rational function of the form:

$$f(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d}$$

where a , b , c and d are complex numbers satisfying $ad - bc \neq 0$, and z is a complex variable. This is the condition satisfied by the elements of the general linear group $GL(n, F)$ over the field of complex numbers. The function $f(z)$ essentially represents the product of the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

with the complex number z , here represented as a column matrix $(z, 1)$. This can be correlated with the irreducible fraction p/q , which produces another irreducible fraction of the form $(ap + bq)/(cp + dq)$ on being operated by the above matrix (see Appendix 2). Here, $p \equiv z$, $q \equiv 1$.

Let us now see what happens if $ad = bc$. Let us assume:

$$f(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d} = k$$

This means:

$$az + b = kcz + kd$$

$$z(a - kc) = kd - b$$

The right-hand side of the above equation is a constant, but the left-hand side depends on the complex variable z . For the above equation to hold for all z , we must have $a - kc = 0$, which means $a/c = k$. And also, since $kd - b = 0$, we also have $b/d = k$. Combining the two equations, we get $a/c = b/d$, which means $ad = bc$.

Thus, when $ad = bc$, the product of the matrices yields a constant function a/c , which is also equal to b/d . A constant function is not bijective and is thus not considered a Möbius transformation (hence the condition $ad - bc \neq 0$).

The inverse of the Möbius transformation $f(z) = (az + b)/(cz + d)$ is another Möbius transformation given by:

⁴¹ A bijective function matches every input to a unique output, and every output to exactly one input – nothing is excluded or repeated.

$$f^{-1}(z) = \frac{dz - b}{-cz + a}$$

which corresponds to the inverse of the above matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} d & -b \\ -c & a \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, we have ignored the scalar multiplication of the inverse matrix by the reciprocal of the determinant of the original matrix, since Möbius transformation is a projective transformation and in a projective space, an element a is equivalent to ka , where k is a scalar.

Geometrically, a Möbius transformation can be obtained by first applying the inverse stereographic projection from the plane to the unit sphere, moving and rotating the sphere to a new location and orientation in space, and then applying a stereographic projection to map from the sphere back to the plane. These transformations preserve angles, map every straight line to a line or circle, and map every circle to a line or circle too.

A **stereographic projection** (see Figure 28) is a perspective projection of the sphere, through a specific point on the sphere (the pole or center of projection), onto a plane perpendicular to the diameter through the point. It is a smooth, bijective function from the entire sphere, except the center of projection to the entire plane. It maps circles on the sphere to circles or lines on the plane, and is conformal, meaning that it preserves angles at which curves meet. It is neither isometric (distance preserving) nor equiareal (area preserving).

*Figure 28: A stereographic projection from the North pole of a sphere onto a plane below.
(Source: Wikipedia.)*

The stereographic projection gives a way to represent a sphere by a plane. The inverse stereographic projection from the plane to the sphere defines a geodesic distance⁴² between points in the plane equal to the spherical distance between the spherical points they represent.

Möbius transformations are essentially the projective transformations of the complex projective line. The points on the complex projective line can be defined as equivalence classes of non-null vectors in the complex vector space C^2 ; two non-null vectors (w, z) and (u, v) are equivalent iff $(w, z) = (\lambda u, \lambda v)$, for some non-zero coefficient $\lambda \in C$.)

The set of all Möbius transformations form a group – the Möbius group – under the operation of function composition. Function composition is a binary operation $*$ that takes two functions f and g , and produces a function $h = g * f$ such that $h(x) = g(f(x))$. A binary operation $*$ on a set A is a function from $A \times A$ into A . For each $(a, b) \in A \times A$, the condition $a * b \in A$ must be satisfied.

The Möbius group is nothing but the projective linear group $PGL(2, C)$. Thus, the modular group $PSL(2, Z)$ is clearly a subgroup of the Möbius group. The group operation of the Möbius group can be taken to be either composition or multiplication of matrices belonging to $GL(2, C)$. Consider the two Möbius transformations $x(z) = (az + b)/(cz + d)$ and $y(z) = (ez + f)/(gz + h)$. Multiplying the corresponding 2×2 matrices associated with these transformations, we get:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ae + bg & af + bh \\ ce + dg & cf + dh \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, the composition of the two functions $x(z)$ and $y(z) - x(y(z)) -$ is:

$$\frac{a \frac{ez + f}{gz + h} + b}{c \frac{ez + f}{gz + h} + d} = \frac{a(ez + f) + b(gz + h)}{c(ez + f) + d(gz + h)} = \frac{(ae + bg)z + (af + bh)}{(ce + dg)z + (cf + dh)}$$

The matrix corresponding to the resulting function is the same matrix we obtained above; both composition as well as matrix multiplication for matrices belonging to $GL(2, C)$ qualify as the group operation of the Möbius group.

Let us now look at fixed points under a Möbius transformation. Every non-identity Möbius transformation has two fixed points γ_1, γ_2 . The fixed points of the Möbius transformation:

$$f(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d}$$

⁴² Geodesic is locally the shortest curve between two points on a curved surface.

are obtained by solving the fixed point equation $f(\gamma) = \gamma$. For $c \neq 0$, this equation has two roots obtained by expanding this equation to:

$$c\gamma^2 - (a - d)\gamma - b = 0$$

and applying the quadratic formula. The roots are:

$$\gamma = \frac{(a - d) \pm \sqrt{(a - d)^2 + 4bc}}{2c}$$

When $c = 0$, the quadratic equation (in terms of γ) degenerates into the linear equation $-(a - d)\gamma - b = 0$. And provided $a \neq d$, the first fixed point is finite and is given by:

$$\gamma = -\frac{b}{a - d}$$

The second fixed point, in this case, is the point at infinity. This is because the point at infinity has the coordinates $[1,0]$, which corresponds to $f(z) = az/cz = a/c$, and a/c is infinity at $c = 0$. This means the Möbius transformation on the point $[1,0]$ (or infinity) gives infinity (provided $c = 0$). Since this point does not change under the transformation, it is a fixed point. In this case ($c = 0, a \neq d$), the transformation is a simple combination of translation, rotation and dilation. It has the form $z \rightarrow \alpha z + \beta$ (putting $c = 0$ in $f(z) = (az + b)/(cz + d)$, we get $f(z) = (az + b)/d = (a/d)z + (b/d) = \alpha z + \beta$, for $\alpha = a/d$ and $\beta = b/d$). In the transformation $z \rightarrow \alpha z + \beta$, multiplying α with z corresponds to a rotation by the argument of α and dilation by the modulus of α (remember a, b, c, d and hence α, β are all complex numbers), and adding β to αz corresponds to a translation by β . If $c = 0$ and $a = d$, there exists no equation in terms of γ , and both the fixed points are at infinity, and the Möbius transformation corresponds to a simple translation $z \rightarrow z + \beta$, where $\beta = b/a$.

Appendix 5: Modular Forms

A modular form is a complex holomorphic⁴³ function on the upper half plane H , satisfying a certain kind of functional equation with respect to the group action of the modular group, and also satisfying a growth condition. In simpler terms, modular forms are special complex functions with symmetry under the modular transformation. If we know how this function behaves inside the fundamental domain D , we can find out how it behaves everywhere else in H . Modular forms must exhibit all the symmetries of the modular group $SL(2, Z)$, plus be holomorphic as well as bounded. Mathematically, a modular form of weight k (k is usually a positive integer, but in some cases, can be a fraction also) for the modular group:

$$SL(2, Z) = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \mid a, b, c, d \in Z, ad - bc = 1 \right\}$$

is a complex-valued function $f(z)$ on the upper half complex plane $H = \{z \in C, \text{Im}(z) > 0\}$, such that $f(z)$ is a holomorphic function on H and $f(z)$ is bounded as $z \rightarrow i\infty$. For any $z \in H$ and any matrix belonging to the modular group $SL(2, Z)$, the **modularity condition** holds:

$$f\left(\frac{az + b}{cz + d}\right) = (cz + d)^k f(z)$$

Let us choose $a = d = -1, b = c = 0$ ($ad - bc = 1$ holds). Putting these values in the above condition, we get $f(z) = (-1)^k f(z)$. For odd values of k , we have $f(z) = -f(z)$. Clearly, only the zero function (a function whose output is always zero) can satisfy this condition, because the output of the function $f(z)$ must also be a complex number, and zero is the only complex number that is its own negative. Solving $a + ib = -(a + ib)$, we get $a = -ib$, which means $a + ib = 0$. Thus, the only modular form of odd weight (k is odd) is the zero function. This result is a general result, and not just for $a = d = -1$, and $b = c = 0$. This is because the matrix with these values of a, b, c and d belongs to $SL(2, Z)$, hence these choices of a, b, c and d are valid. If only the zero function can satisfy the modularity condition for this matrix and for odd k , this means in general, the only modular form of odd weight is the zero function. For arbitrary function, even if the condition holds for some other matrix and odd k , it does not hold for the matrix corresponding to the above choice of a, b, c and d , which is a member of $SL(2, Z)$. For the zero function, the modularity condition will be satisfied for odd k and *any* matrix belonging to $SL(2, Z)$.

Now, if $k = 0$, the modularity condition translates to:

⁴³ A complex function is holomorphic or analytic on a set U if it is complex differentiable at every point of U .

$$f\left(\frac{az+b}{cz+d}\right) = f(z)$$

This means $f(z') = f(z)$, where $z' = (az+b)/(cz+d)$. The output of this function is always constant, regardless of the input. Thus, the only functions satisfying $f(z') = f(z)$, or $f(z) = h$, for some constant h and for $z \in H$, are the constant functions.

Now, as we have seen, the matrices S and T , belonging to $SL(2, Z)$, generate the modular group:

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Substituting the corresponding values of a , b , c and d for S and T in the modularity condition:

$$f\left(\frac{az+b}{cz+d}\right) = (cz+d)^k f(z)$$

we get, respectively for S and T :

$$f\left(-\frac{1}{z}\right) = z^k f(z)$$

$$f(z+1) = f(z)$$

Recall that we define a modular form for the modular group $SL(2, Z)$. Since S and T can generate $SL(2, Z)$, the above conditions are equivalent to the modularity condition. Now, since $f(z+1) = f(z)$, modular forms are periodic functions (with period one), meaning they can be expanded into a **Fourier series**.

Let us look at the Eisenstein series. For $z \in H$, $k \geq 4$ and even values of k , the **Eisenstein series** of weight k is given by:

$$G_k(z) = \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ (m,n) \neq (0,0)}} \frac{1}{(m+nz)^k}$$

The series runs over all integers m and n , provided they are not both zero at the same time. As $k \geq 4$, this series is absolutely convergent.⁴⁴

It can be proved that the Eisenstein series represents a modular form, meaning it is holomorphic, bounded and follows the modularity condition. That the

⁴⁴ A series is absolutely convergent if the sum of the absolute values of all its terms converges to a finite value.

Eisenstein series is bounded can be proved by breaking the series into two parts, for the cases $n = 0$ and $n \neq 0$:

$$G_k(z) = \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ (m,n) \neq (0,0)}} \frac{1}{(m+nz)^k} = \sum_{\substack{m \in \mathbb{Z} \\ m \neq 0}} \frac{1}{m^k} + \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ n \neq 0}} \frac{1}{(m+nz)^k}$$

Since $k \geq 4$, the first series converges to a finite value, and as $\text{Im}(z) \rightarrow \infty$, or equivalently, as $z \rightarrow i\infty$, the second series approaches zero. Thus overall, the sum of both the series is bounded as $z \rightarrow i\infty$.

We can also prove that the Eisenstein series follows the modularity conditions. First, we fix m and replace z by $z + 1$ in the Eisenstein series. We get a similar series, the only change being the replacement of m by $m + n$. But for a fixed m , if we let n run through all the integers, clearly m and $m + n$ will both generate all integers. Hence, both the series are equivalent; $G_k(z) = G_k(z + 1)$.

The second modularity condition can also be easily proved. We start by replacing z with $(-1/z)$ in the Eisenstein series, and proceed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} G_k\left(-\frac{1}{z}\right) &= \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ (m,n) \neq (0,0)}} \frac{1}{(m - n/z)^k} = \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ (m,n) \neq (0,0)}} \frac{z^k}{(zm - n)^k} \\ &= z^k \sum_{\substack{(m,n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ (m,n) \neq (0,0)}} \frac{1}{(zm + n)^k} = z^k G_k(z) \end{aligned}$$

Note that since we span all values of $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, both $(zm - n)$ and $(zm + n)$ are equivalent. Also, we can interchange m and n since both represent the set of all integers and act like dummy variables.

Interestingly, for a given weight $k \geq 4$, the set of modular forms of weight k is a finite-dimensional vector space over the complex numbers. For instance, the space of modular forms of weight $k = 4$ is one-dimensional, which means that there is really only one function that can satisfy these conditions up to scalar multiplication (all other functions that satisfy these conditions can be written as a scalar multiple of this one function). Modular forms also preserve multiplication; if f is a modular form of weight k and g is a modular form of weight k' , then fg is a modular form of weight $k + k'$.

Modular forms have important applications in theoretical high energy physics, the most notable of which is that modular forms are used to model **neutrino masses** and oscillations. Neutrinos are elementary particles that are extremely difficult to detect, and come in three flavors according to the **Standard Model of elementary particles** – the electron neutrino ν_e , the muon neutrino ν_μ and the

tau neutrino ν_τ . These flavors differ from one another mainly in their masses. The existence of neutrinos was predicted to resolve the puzzle of missing energy in beta decay. In beta decay reactions, it was experimentally found that the energy of the products is not equal to the energy of the reactant, thus violating energy conservation. Experimental study of the trajectories of the particles in beta decay experiments inside a gas-filled cloud chamber also indicated a violation of momentum conservation. As charged particles move through the chamber, they ionize the gas molecules in its path, and its trajectory becomes visible. Observations of the trajectories of the emitted particles seemed to suggest violation in momentum conservation.

To resolve this contradiction, the existence of the neutrino was hypothesized, and later experimentally confirmed. Neutrinos are chargeless, hence their trajectories would not be visible inside the cloud chamber. These neutrinos essentially carry away the missing energy in these experiments, and also possess a non-zero momentum, hence resolving the apparent violations of energy and momentum conservation.

Originally, neutrinos were believed to be massless. However, experimental observations of **neutrino oscillations** suggest otherwise. Neutrinos have been observed to “oscillate” from one flavor to another as they travel through space. Experiments showed a mismatch in the number of expected neutrinos of a particular flavor, and further investigations confirmed that neutrinos can actually oscillate between different flavors. We can think of each neutrino flavor as a mix of neutrino mass types, each of which travel at slightly different speeds. As they move, the flavors interfere with one another, and it is possible for one flavor to turn into another.

Now, modular forms do a very good job of modeling neutrino masses and oscillations. The idea is not to somehow explain the observations by increasing the number of parameters in the theory, but to predict the behavior of neutrinos (in the context of neutrino mass and mixing) using symmetry. Neutrino oscillations confirm that neutrinos have mass, and that the mass states of the neutrinos are mixed in a very specific way. Modular forms can model the masses and mixings of neutrinos as arising out of geometry and symmetry, not arbitrary inputs.

The Standard Model of particle physics, in its original form, assumed that neutrinos are massless particles. Thus, the discovery of the neutrino’s mass is a fundamental discovery, studying which might hold the key to understand physics beyond the Standard Model, and also resolve the problems with the Standard Model.

Appendix 6: Congruence Subgroups of the Modular Group

In mathematics, a **congruence subgroup** of a matrix group with integer entries is a subgroup defined by certain congruence conditions on the entries. For example, the subgroup of invertible 2×2 integer matrices with determinant one in which the off-diagonal entries are even is a congruence subgroup.

The **principal congruence subgroup** of level $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $n \geq 1$, of the modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$, is given by:

$$\Gamma(n) = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in SL(2, \mathbb{Z}) : a, d \equiv 1 \pmod{n}; b, c \equiv 0 \pmod{n} \right\}$$

The conditions $a, d \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ and $b, c \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$ are congruence conditions. More specifically, they are called congruence modulo n relations. These relations are equivalence relations. Also, if $a \equiv b \pmod{n}$ and $c \equiv d \pmod{n}$, then $a + c \equiv b + d \pmod{n}$, $a - c \equiv b - d \pmod{n}$, and $ac \equiv bd \pmod{n}$.

The condition $a, d \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ essentially translates to $a \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, read “ a is congruent to one modulo n ”, and $d \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. And since \pmod{n} applies to both sides of the equation, $a \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ actually means $a \pmod{n} = 1 \pmod{n}$, where $a \pmod{n}$ is the remainder obtained on performing the division a/n . For example, if $a = 13$, $n = 5$, $a \pmod{n} = 3$, since the division $13/5$ gives a remainder of 3 (13 is 5 times 2, or 10, plus 3). Clearly $1 \pmod{n}$ is always one, provided $n \neq 0$ (because $1/0$ is undefined). Consider $n = 3$. The division $1/3$ gives a remainder of 1, since 1 is 3 times 0 plus 1.

Now, let us choose $a = 3$, $d = 7$, $n = 2$. Clearly, $a \pmod{n}$ as well as $d \pmod{n}$ is equal to $1 \pmod{n}$, or 1 (3 is 2 times 1 plus 1, 7 is 2 times 3 plus 1). Let $b = 10$, $c = 2$ (n is still 2). Since $0 \pmod{n}$ is always zero (0 is 0 times n plus 0), these values of b , c and n satisfy the condition $b, c \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$. And the above values of a , b , c and d also satisfy $ad - bc = 1$. Thus, the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 3 & 10 \\ 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix}$$

belongs to $\Gamma(2)$ – the principal congruence subgroup of level 2 of the modular group. All such matrices satisfying the required conditions form the principal congruence subgroup of level 2.

Any subgroup of the modular group that contains the principal congruence subgroup is a congruence subgroup of the modular group. Mathematically, a subgroup H of the modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$ is called a congruence subgroup

if there exists some $n \geq 1$ such that H contains the principal congruence subgroup $\Gamma(n)$. The level of H is the smallest such n . Modular forms of level 1 (modular forms defined over a level 1 congruence subgroup of the modular group) are essentially defined over the full modular group, because the conditions $a, d \equiv 1 \pmod{1}$ and $b, c \equiv 0 \pmod{1}$ are satisfied by any set of integers a, b, c and d such that $ad - bc = 1$. This means the congruence subgroup of level 1 is the full modular group itself. For $n > 1$ (higher levels), we can define modular forms that are defined over the corresponding congruence subgroup of the modular group. Clearly, congruence subgroups of the modular group are more constrained as compared to the full modular group, especially as we move to higher levels.

Studying congruence subgroups of the modular group is also useful in theoretical high energy physics. Two-dimensional conformal field theories can often be defined on a torus, which is a geometry having modular symmetry. Higher dimensional quantum field theories are also often compactified on a torus or other similar periodic geometries. In such a theory, certain physical quantities must be invariant under modular transformations. Sometimes, only a congruence subgroup of the modular group becomes relevant; not all the elements of the group satisfy the physical constraints, like boundary conditions or discrete symmetries.

Appendix 7: Python Codes used for $H \rightarrow D$ Transformations

In the Python codes used for the $H \rightarrow D$ transformations shown in Figures 21 – 25, we have used the Shapely module to define the fundamental domain D and the different regions on the upper half plane H . Then we have defined the S and T transformations, and the different combinations of S and T for each region. Finally, we have plotted the original points in H (uniformly and randomly distributed), and the corresponding transformed points. We have outlined the boundaries of the fundamental domain in black, and colored the original and transformed points differently.

It is important to recall that in our codes, we have *not* excluded the right boundaries (in the first quadrant) from the fundamental domain D ; and also, we have not considered original points in H lying very close to the real axis.

The code used for generating the output shown in Figure 21 is given below. The code was run on the Google Colab platform using Python3. In this code, we have generated 20000 points in H , and we have ensured no point in H has a vertical coordinate less than 0.3.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point, Polygon
from shapely.geometry.polygon import Polygon
from shapely.geometry import box

xmin, ymin = -1e10, 0
xmax, ymax = -0.5, 1e10
region1 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
xmin, ymin = 0.5, 0
xmax, ymax = 1e10, 1e10
region2 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
xmin, ymin = -1e10, 0
xmax, ymax = 1e10, 1e10
region3 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
center_x, center_y = 0, 0
radius = 1.0
circle = Point(center_x, center_y).buffer(radius)
fundamentalregion =
region3.difference(region1.union(region2).union(circle))
regionH = region3.difference(fundamentalregion)
def S(x,y):
```

```

    return (-x/(x**2+y**2), y/(x**2+y**2))
def T(x,a):
    return x+a

rec = Polygon([(0.5,0), (0.5,1e10), (1.5,1e10), (1.5,0)])
recneg = Polygon([(-1.5,0), (-1.5,1e10), (-0.5,1e10), (-0.5,0)])
fundreg= Polygon([(-0.5,0), (-0.5,1e10), (0.5,1e10), (0.5,0)])
circ1 = Point(1,0).buffer(radius)
circ2 = Point(-1,0).buffer(radius)
circ3 = Point(2,0).buffer(radius)
circ4 = Point(-2,0).buffer(radius)

num_points = 20000
x = np.random.uniform(-1.5, 1.5, num_points)
y = np.random.uniform(0.3, 15, num_points)
points = np.array([x, y]).T
inside = [regionH.contains(Point(point)) for point in points]
X = x[inside]
Y = y[inside]

Pt = np.array([X,Y]).T

ins = [rec.difference(circ1).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X1 = X[ins]
Y1 = Y[ins]
X1 = T(X1,-1)

ins = [recneg.difference(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X2 = X[ins]
Y2 = Y[ins]
X2 = T(X2,1)

ins =
[circle.intersection(fundreg).difference(circ1).difference(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X3 = X[ins]
Y3 = Y[ins]
X3,Y3 = S(X3,Y3)

ins =
[fundreg.difference(circle).intersection(circ1).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X4 = X[ins]
Y4 = Y[ins]
X4,Y4 = S(X4,Y4)
X4 = T(X4,1)

```

```

ins = [fundreg.intersection(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]
X5 = X[ins]
Y5 = Y[ins]
X5,Y5= S(X5,Y5)
X5 = T(X5,-1)

ins =
[circ2.intersection(recneg).difference(circ4).difference(circle).contai
ns(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X6 = X[ins]
Y6 = Y[ins]
X6 = T(X6,1)
X6,Y6= S(X6,Y6)

ins =
[circ1.intersection(rec).difference(circ3).difference(circle).contains(
Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X7 = X[ins]
Y7 = Y[ins]
X7 = T(X7,-1)
X7,Y7= S(X7,Y7)

ins = [circle.intersection(recneg).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]
X8 = X[ins]
Y8 = Y[ins]
X8 = T(X8,1)
X8,Y8= S(X8,Y8)
X8 = T(X8,1)

ins = [circle.intersection(rec).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X9 = X[ins]
Y9 = Y[ins]
X9 = T(X9,-1)
X9,Y9 = S(X9,Y9)
X9= T(X9,-1)

ins = [circ4.intersection(recneg).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]
X10 = X[ins]
Y10 = Y[ins]
X10 = T(X10,1)
X10,Y10= S(X10,Y10)
X10 = T(X10,-1)

ins = [circ3.intersection(recneg).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]

```

```

X11 = X[ins]
Y11 = Y[ins]
X11 = T(X11,-1)
X11,Y11= S(X11,Y11)
X11 = T(X11,1)

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))

Xfundcir = np.arange(-0.5,0.6,0.1)
Yfundcir = np.sqrt(1-Xfundcir**2)

if(max(Y)>max(y)):
    Yfundline = np.linspace(0.867,max(Y),2)
else:
    Yfundline = np.linspace(0.867,max(y),2)

Xfundleft = np.ones(len(Yfundline))*-0.5
Xfundright = np.ones(len(Yfundline))*0.5

plt.scatter(X, Y, s=3, color = 'skyblue', label='Original Points')
plt.scatter(X1,Y1, s=3, color = 'green', label = 'Transformed points')
plt.scatter(X2,Y2, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X3,Y3, s=3, color='green')
plt.scatter(X4,Y4, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X5,Y5, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X6,Y6, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X7,Y7, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X8,Y8, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X9,Y9, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X10,Y10, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X11,Y11, s=3, color = 'green')
plt.plot(Xfundcir,Yfundcir,'k-')
plt.plot(Xfundcir,Yfundcir,'k-',label='Fundamental domain boundaries')
plt.plot(Xfundleft,Yfundline,'k-',Xfundright,Yfundline,'k-')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Transformations from H to D (Modular Group)')
plt.xlabel('Real axis')
plt.ylabel('Imaginary axis')
plt.show()

```

The code used for generating the output shown in Figure 22 is given below. In this code, we have generated 20000 points in H , and ensured no point in H has a vertical coordinate less than 0.3. But in addition, we have colored different groups of transformed points differently, based on the region in H they originated in, as outlined in Table 1.

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point, Polygon
from shapely.geometry.polygon import Polygon
from shapely.geometry import box

xmin, ymin = -1e10, 0
xmax, ymax = -0.5, 1e10
region1 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
xmin, ymin = 0.5, 0
xmax, ymax = 1e10, 1e10
region2 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
xmin, ymin = -1e10, 0
xmax, ymax = 1e10, 1e10
region3 = Polygon([(xmin, ymin), (xmin, ymax), (xmax, ymax), (xmax,
ymin)])
center_x, center_y = 0, 0
radius = 1.0
circle = Point(center_x, center_y).buffer(radius)
fundamentalregion =
region3.difference(region1.union(region2).union(circle))
regionH = region3.difference(fundamentalregion)

def S(x,y):
    return (-x/(x**2+y**2), y/(x**2+y**2))

def T(x,a):
    return x+a

rec = Polygon([(0.5,0), (0.5,1e10), (1.5,1e10), (1.5,0)])
recneg = Polygon([(-1.5,0), (-1.5,1e10), (-0.5,1e10), (-0.5,0)])
fundreg= Polygon([(-0.5,0), (-0.5,1e10), (0.5,1e10), (0.5,0)])
circ1 = Point(1,0).buffer(radius)
circ2 = Point(-1,0).buffer(radius)
circ3 = Point(2,0).buffer(radius)
circ4 = Point(-2,0).buffer(radius)

num_points = 20000
x = np.random.uniform(-1.5, 1.5, num_points)
y = np.random.uniform(0.3, 15, num_points)
points = np.array([x, y]).T
inside = [regionH.contains(Point(point)) for point in points]
X = x[inside]
Y = y[inside]

Pt = np.array([X,Y]).T

```

```

ins = [rec.difference(circ1).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X1 = X[ins]
Y1 = Y[ins]
X1 = T(X1,-1)

ins = [recneg.difference(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X2 = X[ins]
Y2 = Y[ins]
X2 = T(X2,1)

ins =
[circle.intersection(fundreg).difference(circ1).difference(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X3 = X[ins]
Y3 = Y[ins]
X3,Y3 = S(X3,Y3)

ins =
[fundreg.intersection(circle).intersection(circ1).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X4 = X[ins]
Y4 = Y[ins]
X4,Y4 = S(X4,Y4)
X4 = T(X4,1)

ins =
[fundreg.intersection(circle).intersection(circ2).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X5 = X[ins]
Y5 = Y[ins]
X5,Y5= S(X5,Y5)
X5 = T(X5,-1)

ins =
[circ2.intersection(recneg).difference(circ4).difference(circle).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X6 = X[ins]
Y6 = Y[ins]
X6 = T(X6,1)
X6,Y6= S(X6,Y6)

ins =
[circ1.intersection(rec).difference(circ3).difference(circle).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X7 = X[ins]
Y7 = Y[ins]
X7 = T(X7,-1)
X7,Y7= S(X7,Y7)

```

```

ins = [circle.intersection(recneg).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]
X8 = X[ins]
Y8 = Y[ins]
X8 = T(X8,1)
X8,Y8= S(X8,Y8)
X8 = T(X8,1)

ins = [circle.intersection(rec).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X9 = X[ins]
Y9 = Y[ins]
X9 = T(X9,-1)
X9,Y9 = S(X9,Y9)
X9= T(X9,-1)

ins = [circ4.intersection(recneg).contains(Point(point)) for point in
Pt]
X10 = X[ins]
Y10 = Y[ins]
X10 = T(X10,1)
X10,Y10= S(X10,Y10)
X10 = T(X10,-1)

ins = [circ3.intersection(rec).contains(Point(point)) for point in Pt]
X11 = X[ins]
Y11 = Y[ins]
X11 = T(X11,-1)
X11,Y11= S(X11,Y11)
X11 = T(X11,1)

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))

Xfundcir = np.arange(-0.5,0.6,0.1)
Yfundcir = np.sqrt(1-Xfundcir**2)

if(max(Y)>max(y)):
    Yfundline = np.linspace(0.867,max(Y),2)
else:
    Yfundline = np.linspace(0.867,max(y),2)

Xfundleft = np.ones(len(Yfundline))*-0.5
Xfundright = np.ones(len(Yfundline))*0.5
plt.scatter(X, Y, s=5, label='Original Points', color='skyblue')
plt.scatter(X1,Y1, s=5, color = 'lightgreen')
plt.scatter(X2,Y2, s=5, color = 'lightgreen')
plt.scatter(X3,Y3, s=5, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X4,Y4, s=5, color = 'green')
plt.scatter(X5,Y5, s=5, color = 'green')

```

```
plt.scatter(X6,Y6, s=5, color='goldenrod')
plt.scatter(X7,Y7, s=5, color='goldenrod')
plt.scatter(X8,Y8, s=5, color='purple')
plt.scatter(X9,Y9, s=5, color='purple')
plt.scatter(X10,Y10, s=5, color='red')
plt.scatter(X11,Y11, s=5, color='red')
plt.plot(Xfundcir,Yfundcir,'k-',label='Fundamental domain boundaries')
plt.plot(Xfundleft,Yfundline,'k-',Xfundright,Yfundline,'k-')
plt.title('Transformations from H to D (Modular Group)')
plt.legend()
plt.xlabel('Real axis')
plt.ylabel('Imaginary axis')
plt.show()
```

The outputs shown in Figures 23 – 25 can be generated in a similar manner, by changing the number of original points and the minimum allowed vertical coordinate accordingly in the above code.